

Global Burden of Animal Diseases (GBADs) Technical Guide

Version 1.0 (July 2024)

Suggested citation: Global Burden of Animal Diseases (GBADs) (2024), *Technical Guide (version 1.0)* 2024. Global Burden of Animal Diseases programme, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11093240

Document Version Control

Version	Date	Author	Change Description
1.0	31 st July 2024	Ellen Hughes	Document Created

Preface

Livestock are vital to the global economy, food security, and individual livelihoods, yet animal disease burdens are incomplete and therefore poorly understood. Understanding animal disease burdens is hampered by data access, and availability of agreed methods of assessment. The Global Burden of Animal Diseases (GBADs) programme is addressing these limitations through the development of a systematic and reproducible analytical framework that can generate animal disease burden estimates at global, country and local levels. The GBADs Technical Guide (version 1.0) describes this analytical framework and presents the current methodologies used by GBADs in five core areas of analysis: estimation of livestock biomass, estimation of the economic value of livestock, the Animal Health Loss Envelope, attribution to disease, and assessment of the wider economic impact of animal disease burdens.

The assessment of disease burdens is well advanced in human health through work that began over 50 years ago (Hausman, 2020). In animal health there has been more focus on the economic assessment of interventions, particularly in the management of infectious diseases that have significant trade implications. Yet there has been a growing awareness of the need to look at the overall economic assessment of disease, with theoretical frameworks from John McInerney (1996) tweaked by Clem Tisdell (2009) and updated by David Hennessey and Tom Marsh (2021). There have also been some attempts to implement these frameworks at country scale through the work led by Richard Bennett (2003) in Great Britain on endemic livestock diseases and at a global scale with studies on FMD (Knight-Jones & Rushton, 2013) and coccidiosis (Blake *et al.*, 2020). In 2015, I was requested by OIE (now known as WOAH) to determine the level of knowledge of the costs and benefits of animal disease at the chief veterinary office level. Will Gilbert supported me in conducting and analysing a survey that revealed gaps in data and information (Rushton & Gilbert, 2016). This led to an OIE resolution (No 35, (OIE, 2016)) that recommended the development and testing of a framework for the assessment of the burden of animal diseases.

Emerging from this has been the need to assess livestock disease from an economic perspective. We recognise that livestock are both a part of the societal economies and play a fundamental role in the cultural and social fabric of many societies. Yet the livestock sectors are placed under ministries that reflect the need for these animals to be part of the economy, using discount rates that reflect economic rather than social rates of return. Therefore, meaningful assessments of animal disease burden need to explore both the loss of production and expenditure and how this shift in the efficiency of supply of livestock and their products impacts markets and therefore consumers.

In 2018 the GBADs programme was initiated as a multi-institutional, international collaboration (Rushton *et al.*, 2018), led by the University of Liverpool¹ and supported by the World Organisation of Animal Health. The first steps towards the GBADs Technical Guide began with the rollout of the programme with the development and testing of methods to estimate the animal disease burdens (Rushton *et al.*, 2021). This implementation has been carried out by GBADs consortium members. Our early work has focused on country case studies and the Technical Guide provides details on these methods, as well as implications for the global estimates. With this guide we aim to provide researchers, veterinary services, and other animal health professionals with technical guidance on how to implement GBADs methods.

¹ <https://animalhealthmetrics.org/about-us-2/>

The guide provides a foundation in the process of undertaking a burden assessment, which may be further supported by scientific papers and other peer-reviewed GBADs outputs, and if appropriate through development of collaborations with the GBADs programme. Additionally, for policy makers and those principally interested in GBADs output, the Guide provides insight into how estimates are derived and interpreted, in a form more accessible than academic papers and other GBADs technical outputs.

The current document is version 1.0 of the GBADs Technical Guide and as such outlines the current approaches used within the programme. These methodologies, which are in use in country case-studies across the world, will continue to be expanded and refined. New approaches may be added as the programme moves into different areas of focus, such as additional species or production systems, and further research questions arise. With these developments in mind, it is important to note that the current guide represents working methods and not a final product. Each chapter of this guide is a working document, outlining the present version of living methods that will change and develop over time, as additional research is conducted, and further case-studies implemented.

As a programme, we are keen to engage and work with governments, institutions and individuals who are interested in estimating the burden of animal diseases in their context of interest. We encourage readers of this Technical Guide to engage with the GBADs programme, and welcome feedback from users on the utility of the guide as well as the methods themselves.

Each chapter is authored by members of the GBADs consortium leading on the different methodologies. However, all the work in this Guide and its chapters builds on collaborative teamwork from all members of the GBADs consortium, as well as our country-level partners.

The GBADs Technical Guide is based on research funded by the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO). The findings and conclusions contained within are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect positions or policies of the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation and FCDO.

Jonathan Rushton

Director GBADs

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Acknowledgments

GBADs is a collaborative programme that believes in working together so we can go far and achieve more. Hence the GBADs Technical Guide has been a team effort of authors, coordinators and reviewers who have all been supported by generous funders. Authors are listed after each chapter title and the other key contributors are listed below. We also recognise that the guide was only made possible by the wider GBADs team, details of whom can be found on our [website](#)².

Funders

Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation – many thanks for their support and to the livestock team in particular Shannon Mesenhowski, Nick Juleff and Sam Thevasagayam.

Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO) – many thanks for their support and to Research, Evidence and Development team in particular Lucie Kelleher, Alan Tollervey, Tim Leyland and Rachel Lambert

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We thank the WOAAH review panel (for chapter 3, Economic Value) consisting of Edna Massay Kallon, WOAAH; Yohane Soko, WOAAH; Rahul Srivastava, WOAAH; Paolo Tizzani, WOAAH; Laure Weber-Vintzel, WOAAH.

We are grateful to the Reference Group review panel (convened by WOAAH, chapter 3 Economic Value) members, Amy Hagerman, Oklahoma State University, USA; Walter Okelo, CSIRO, Australia; Misheck Mulumba, Agricultural Research Council, South Africa

We also thank Tessa Cornell, University of Liverpool, UK and Folorunso Fasina, FAO for reviewing drafts of the manuscript.

² <https://animalhealthmetrics.org/about-us-2/>

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Abbreviations

AHLE	Animal Health Loss Envelope
CGE	Computable General Equilibrium
CSIRO	Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation
DPM	Dynamic population model
EDM	equilibrium displacement model
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
FAOSTAT	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations statistical database
FMD	Foot-and-mouth disease
FMDv	Foot-and-mouth disease virus
GBADs	Global Burden of Animal Diseases
GBD	Global Burden of Diseases
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GTAP	Global Trade Analysis Project Model
ILRI	International Livestock Research Institute
KE	GBADs Knowledge Engine
PE	Partial Equilibrium
PPR	Peste des petits ruminants
PPRV	Peste des petits ruminants virus
SDG	Sustainable development goal
SEBI	Supporting Evidence Based Interventions
TCF	Technical conversion factor
TLU	Tropical Livestock Unit
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System
VIPEL	Vertically Integrated Partial Equilibrium Livestock
WAHIS	World Animal Health Information System
WOAH	World Organisation for Animal Health

Definitions

Aetiology	The relationship between causes and the effects they produce.
Animal Health Ontology	An ontology developed as a standardised ontology for animal health with the purpose of providing consistent, reusable and sustainable description of animal disease terms. It includes terms to describe the populations and demographics of animals together with the impacts of the disease on production.
Asset	A resource, e.g. live farmed animals, that is controlled by entities, e.g. smallholders, businesses or countries, because of past events, e.g. inputs to production, and which is expected to provide future benefits for those entities.
Asset value	The monetary value of assets (live farmed animals). It refers to the price and quantity at which they are traded in a market at a specific point in time. Only farmed animals are included in this value definition for the purpose of this guide. No other farm assets or liabilities are considered here.
Benign	A process that is mild in nature and not dangerous to health.
Burden of animal disease	The impact of disease in a farmed animal population, including morbidity, mortality, and health expenditure. For GBADs this incorporates the impact on the wider economy and human health. This impact refers to various metrics to measure death, loss of health due to, and expenditure on, diseases and risk factors.
Comorbidity	The coexistence of two or more disease processes in the same animal or groups of animals.
Conceptual disease model	Computational models, schematically represented as an outcome tree, that describe the significant outcomes (sequelae or syndromes) of each aetiological cause, the various health states that best represent the health loss from each sequela, as well as the time spent in each health state.
Control inputs	Inputs to the production process which are provided specifically in response to, or as prophylaxis against, disease.
Cost of disease	The sum of losses and expenditure attributable to the presence, or risk, of disease.
Direct use value	The value derived from the consumptive use or utilisation of farmed animals. Direct use values include a) live animals that are traded in markets, b) primary and secondary outputs that animals generate that are traded in markets, e.g. meat, milk, eggs, skins/hides, wool, manure, and c) services provided by animals, e.g. transportation, draught power, insurance, and financial services (collateral for loans, financial security, livelihood protection).
Disease	An abnormal condition that adversely affects the structure or function leading to an inability to perform physiologic functions at normal levels; the outcome of which is a decreased efficiency of converting inputs such as feed and water, into outputs such as milk and meat.
Economic Agent	An economic agent refers to any individual, group, or entity that makes economic decisions or takes economic actions within an economy. Economic

agents in the economics model refers to consumers, firms, factor suppliers, government, etc.

Economic Shocks	Economic shocks are regarded exogenous in the equilibrium models which can arise from various sources. For example, a positive demand shock could originate from changes in consumer behaviour or preferences, e.g., in meat consumption. Similarly, a positive supply shock could arise from productivity increases due to reduced animal health burdens (e.g., fewer disease outbreaks) and lead to increases in livestock and livestock products.
Economic value	Used here as a synonym for direct use value (see above).
Economic Welfare	Economic welfare refers to the economic well-being or prosperity of individuals, households, or society as a whole within an economy. Economic well-being could mean different things for producer and consumers. For example, economic well-being for producers implies profitability increase and/or production cost decrease for producers, which is referred to as producer welfare. On the other hand, consumer welfare refers to consumer well-being, which could be determined by factors such as lower price, higher income etc.
Enterprise budget	A method for representing the relationship between the inputs (land and feed, animals, labour etc) provided to a particular enterprise on farm, and the outputs generated, valued by their respective prices, over a specified time period. A farm may operate multiple enterprises as part of the farm business, for example a dairy enterprise would be distinct to a laying hen enterprise on the same farm.
Enterprise profit	The total revenue of a farm enterprise, minus the fixed and variable costs attributable to it.
Exogenous	Refers to factors or variables that are external to the economic models described in chapter 6. These exogenous factors are assumed to be outside the control of the economic agents within the models.
Expenditure	The spending of a family or firm due to the presence or risk of disease. This includes both increased cost of ordinary and disease control inputs.
Externalities, External effects	A cost or benefit which does not accrue only to those performing the activity which produces it. Negative externalities impose a cost, while positive externalities generate a benefit. Examples of negative externalities include air, water, and noise pollution.
Farm budget	A method for representing the relationship between the inputs (land and feed, animals, labour etc) provided to all the enterprises on farm, and the outputs generated, valued by their respective prices, over a specified time period.
Firm	The basic unit of organisation for economically productive activities, which convert inputs to outputs. A firm can range in size from a single individual operating a business to a large company.
Gross Margin	The total revenue of an enterprise less the variable costs attributable to it.
Health state	Reflects a combination of sequelae that result in production loss which is not necessarily unique to a particular disease. Each health state is associated with

a change in the value of a production parameter that reflects the severity of effect.

Ideal health state	A normality in bodily structure and function that provides the ability to perform physiologic functions at normal levels, given nutrition and other environmental requirements are provided at adequate levels. There is no health lost to disease, and therefore also no expenditure on disease control.
Litter size	The number of animals born per litter. It is measured as a distribution, for example proportion of single, twins and multiple lambs in a litter per adult ewe.
Livestock biomass	The aggregate liveweight of a population of farmed animals, typically expressed in a weight-based unit, e.g. tonnes.
Losses	Reduced volume of output or associated price due to disease, leading to lost revenue.
Market value	Value of assets (live animals) and outputs that is derived from the demand and supply in markets, which determines a market selling price. The term market value is used as a synonym for current market value.
Market-based approach	Method of determining the economic value of assets (live animals) and outputs based on the market selling price.
Monetary value	Value of a good or service that is expressed in monetary terms. It reflects what individuals are willing to pay for a good or service in the market. The term is a synonym for price.
Morbidity	A measure of disease incorporating a disease frequency, the clinical manifestation of the disease, resulting health states and changes in the value of production parameters.
Mortality rate	The proportion of the population that die during the study period. Mortality is a complex and multi-faceted parameter and may be defined differently depending on circumstances. In GBADs the parameter "mortality rate" is used to refer to deaths directly due to animal health-related causes including: disease, injury, predation, acute nutritional deficits (e.g. starvation), and environmental catastrophe (e.g. droughts, flooding, wildfire). It does not include emergency slaughter or salvage slaughter as these are included in offtake if they have financial value.
Ontology	A terminology that includes explicit formal specification of how to represent the objects, concepts, relationships, and other entities that are in the terminology.
Ordinary inputs	Inputs to the production process which are provided to animals irrespective of their health state.
Output value	The monetary value of primary outputs (meat, milk, eggs) and secondary outputs (manure, hides, wool, etc.). It refers to the price and quantity at which they are traded at a market at a specific point in time.
Parturition interval	The time interval between successive parturitions in the same female animal.

Parturition rate	The inverse of the parturition interval. The value is the median or mean number of litters per adult female per time interval.
Performance	Animal performance refers to productivity of an animal relative to another.
Price	The monetary value, i.e. value expressed in monetary terms, of a good or service. It is derived from its demand and supply in the market in which it is traded and reflects individuals' willingness to pay for a good or service. The term is here also used as a synonym for (current) market selling price.
Production	The process by which an economic entity (firm or household) converts inputs to outputs which are either sold, or consumed within the household.
Productivity	The rate of output production per unit of input. A measure of the efficiency of the production process. Common measures of livestock productivity include feed conversion ratios, output per unit of land, or per metre-squared of floor space.
Sensitivity (diagnostics)	The probability that a diagnostic test will produce a positive result given the animal is infected or affected by the disease of interest. The sensitivity of a test can be determined by calculating the number of true positive results divided by the sum of true positive results plus number of false negative results.
Sequela	The pathological condition resulting from a disease or injury, such as abortion. Each sequela may be a consequence of multiple aetiologies and can be mapped to one or more health states resulting in a change in the value of a production parameter.
Specificity (diagnostic)	The probability that a diagnostic test will produce a negative result given the animal is not infected or affected by the disease of interest. The specificity of a test can be determined by calculating the number of true negative results divided by the sum of true negative results plus number of false positive results.
Statistical imputation	The substitution of some value for a missing data point or missing component of a data point.
Value	The weighting/importance that individuals place on something, e.g. a good or service, which reflects the utility or benefit that they gain from it. Value of a good or service does not always equal the price of a good or service, as it also includes intangible benefits, e.g. enjoyment, social status, and so may exceed the monetary value of goods and services.

Chapter 1 Introduction

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1.1 The Global Burden of Animal Diseases (GBADs) programme

The health of farmed animals, both terrestrial and aquatic, is important globally to ensure animal welfare, public health, and human nutritional and food security, as well as to support people's livelihoods, e.g. as a source of income, status, or insurance (Mehrabi *et al.*, 2020). Despite this, information about the economic and social impact of animal diseases on farmed animal systems is limited, at both global and national scales. Moreover, there has been no systematic approach for assessing the impact of animal diseases and their implications for human society. Globally, the burden of animal diseases is believed to be high, but measuring this burden is challenging, and novel, systematic methods are needed to make accurate estimations at national and global level.

The Global Burden of Animal Diseases (GBADs) programme is an alliance of organisations, led by The University of Liverpool, that aims to tackle these challenges through the development of innovative methods for estimating the burden of animal diseases. The programme aims to collect, validate, analyse, and disseminate information on livestock production and economic effects of animal diseases. This information will serve as a baseline for evidence-based policy-making and it will contribute to the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), specifically the goals related to health (SDG 3), nutrition (SDGs 2 & 12), the environment (SDGs 13, 14 & 15), and poverty (SDG 1) (Rushton *et al.*, 2018).

Since its inception in 2018 (Rushton *et al.*, 2018), the GBADs programme has developed and tested a collection of methodologies for estimating global, national, and subnational animal disease burdens, examining impacts both at the farm level and across the wider economy. Methodologies have been developed across the four focus areas of the GBADs programme, namely i) livestock populations, ii) the Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE), iii) the attribution of losses to specific causes, and iv) the impact of losses across the economy. These four areas form the basis of the GBADs analytical framework, set out in Figure 1. In the area of *livestock populations*, GBADs works on estimations of biomass and the economic value (i.e. direct use value) of farmed livestock, which falls under the topic, 'economic investment in animals and infrastructure' in the analytical framework (Figure 1.1). In the area of the *Animal Health Loss Envelope*, GBADs works to assess how much we are losing and how much we are spending on animal health. In the area of *Attribution* work focuses on assessing the absolute and relative burden of different diseases. Finally, in the area of *Impacts of Animal Disease Across the Broader Economy*, GBADs works to identify who across society is most affected.

³ [GBADs – Global Burden of Animal Diseases \(animalhealthmetrics.org\)](https://animalhealthmetrics.org/)

Figure 1.1 Analytical framework for the Global Burden of Animal Diseases programme.

Adapted from Rushton et al. (2021). Note: The figure illustrates the four focus areas of the GBADs programme (rectangular boxes).

Each aspect of the analytical framework is important for the development of a unified understanding of the impacts of animal disease burdens, but each element also has independent value and may have application beyond the framework outlined here.

Guided by the framework, GBADs has produced multiple outputs that summarise various elements in the assessment of livestock production and the economic effects of animal diseases. These outputs include workshops, [dashboards](#)⁴ and [publications](#)⁵. In addition to these outputs, GBADs has developed five living technical guides that form the chapters of the present document, and which span the four focus areas outlined above. The methods set out in the GBADs Technical Guide encompass the key approaches currently in use across the GBADs programme and cover the main aspects of animal disease burden estimation.

1.2 Purpose of the GBADs Technical Guide

The GBADs Technical Guide is designed to provide guidance on implementing and interpreting key GBADs methodologies. It is a working document and will be updated as methods evolve, reflecting the ongoing development and refinement of GBADs analytical approaches.

1.2.1 Scope

The five chapters of the GBADs Technical Guides cover GBADs methodologies across all four focus areas of the programme. There are two chapters for the first area, *Livestock Populations*, and one each for the other three areas, as follows:

1. Estimating livestock biomass
2. Estimating the economic value of farmed animals
3. Estimating the Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE)
4. Attributing the burden of animal disease to specific causes
5. Assessing the wider economic impact of animal disease burdens

Each chapter sets out the background to and overview of the approach, a description of the methods and the data required, and guidance on interpreting the results. Links to other resources, including published papers on the methods described and sample R code, are included where appropriate.

⁴ <https://www.gbadske.org/dashboards>

⁵ <https://animalhealthmetrics.org/publications/>

Please note that code development and optimisation is ongoing. The GitHub repositories linked to in the GBADs Technical Guide record this development and provide example code. This code may need to be adapted for further use and so should not be seen as ready-to-use without further exploration and confirmation that it is appropriate to the needs of the user.

1.2.2 Target audience

This technical guide is intended to be used by individuals or groups who wish to undertake some or all elements of a burden of animal disease assessment, for terrestrial or aquatic farmed species, using GBADs methodologies. Potential users include national or regional government organisations, private companies such as livestock insurers and finance institutions, livestock production system analysts, and academics. The level of prior knowledge required varies for each chapter, but a basic understanding of topic-specific principles (e.g. economics, disease attribution) is recommended. In addition, the guides will provide insights into how to interpret the information generated by the GBADs methodologies for policy-makers and other stakeholders.

1.2.3 How to use this guide

Each chapter has stand-alone value, as well as forming part of the GBADs analytical framework (Figure 1.1). Users may wish to pursue only one methodology (e.g. calculation of biomass), but we encourage users to consider the wider analytical framework, and how methods presented in the other chapters could be useful in helping to achieve the goals of the animal disease burden assessments they are undertaking.

We intend for the GBADs Technical Guide to provide instructions on how to conduct the methodologies currently in use across the GBADs programme and anticipate that the information provided will allow users to adapt these methods to their own data and research questions. To this end, the guides are intentionally written in accessible and non-technical language where possible. However, it is important for users of this Guide to note that the methods described continue to be refined by the GBADs programme and are at different stages of development. For readers who want to explore the methods further, links are provided throughout the text to published academic papers and other resources, which provide additional technical details of the methods outlined. Users are encouraged to reach out to the GBADs programme if further specific guidance or technical support is required or to provide feedback, via gbads@liverpool.ac.uk.

1.2.4 Other resources

In addition to the links mentioned above, further details of the GBADs programme, current outputs, and the GBADs knowledge engine can be found here:

The **GBADs** website - <https://animalhealthmetrics.org>

The **GBADs** Knowledge Engine - <https://www.gbadske.org/dashboards>

1.2.5 Versions

The GBADs technical guide will be updated as methodologies evolve. Review of the methods will be conducted on a rolling basis. Each area of analysis, outlined in the different chapters, will be reviewed independently, as methods may be refined or expanded at different rates, depending on the requirements of the method and outcomes of ongoing and future research and implementation. This document is version 1.0.

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Chapter 2 Estimating livestock biomass

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Abstract

This chapter of the GBADs Technical Guide presents methods to estimate the biomass of terrestrial livestock species using data from different sources and with different granularities. Livestock biomass, the aggregate liveweight of a given population of animals, can be used as a denominator for comparing disease burdens, the value of livestock, antimicrobial use, and other characteristics of livestock systems. It allows comparison of inputs, outputs, and production losses, per unit, across species, production systems and countries. It is also used in the calculation of Economic Value (Chapter 3) and shares common input data with the Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE) (Chapter 4) calculations.

⁶ [GBADs – Global Burden of Animal Diseases \(animalhealthmetrics.org\)](https://animalhealthmetrics.org/)

2.1 Introduction

Livestock biomass is the aggregate liveweight of a given population of animals, for example, all cattle in Ethiopia. Unlike other common units such as Tropical Livestock Units (TLUs), which represent the weight of a “typical” animal, livestock biomass is measured in kilograms (kg) and better accounts for variations in the breed, age, and sex of animals within a population, giving it the flexibility to be used across vastly different production systems. Estimating the biomass of livestock is the first component of the methodologies used to characterise *livestock populations* in the GBADs analytical framework, set out in Figure 1.1.

In the context of GBADs, biomass is used as a denominator for comparing inputs, outputs, and production losses per unit (kg of livestock biomass) across species, production systems and countries. When considering similar animals under common conditions comparison may be made per head (i.e., by the number of individuals) but this approach presents several important disadvantages, especially when comparing on a larger scale. Different species of livestock vary in size, with individual liveweight also influenced by factors including breed, sex, age or growth stage, and nutritional status of an animal, all of which vary between countries and production systems. Because of this variation, comparing the burden of animal disease between populations on a per head basis may be misleading, and a denominator that accounts for these differences is required. Depending on the purpose of the analysis, human population size, value of livestock production, or Gross Domestic Product (GDP) could also be used as denominators.

Biomass is also used as an input into calculations of the economic value of livestock as described in Chapter 3 (see also Schrobback *et al.* (2023)), and is used in the calculation of current productivity in the animal health loss envelope (AHLE) model described in Chapter 4 (see also Gilbert *et al.* (2023)). Beyond GBADs, the biomass of livestock can be used in the assessment of natural resource use (Addy & Thomas, 1978), environmental impacts (Steinfeld & Gerber, 2010) and use of antimicrobials (Gochez *et al.*, 2019). It could also be used to estimate market demand for veterinary products or feed additives that are administered according to liveweight or feed intake (Smith *et al.*, 2024).

This chapter outlines methods to estimate the biomass of livestock depending on the type and quality of data available. The methods are applicable from local to global scales, depending on the data used. Guidance is provided on how to select the most appropriate method and we discuss factors that influence the accuracy of different datasets, with further information available in (Li *et al.*, 2024). Links to R code in [GitHub](#) and associated documentation are provided which offer practical advice on how the analysis could be undertaken⁷. Please note that code development and optimisation is ongoing. The linked GitHub repositories record this development and provide example code, which may need to be adapted for further use.

This guide is intended to inform policy makers and implementers, livestock production system analysts, researchers and stakeholders who may be interested in the use of biomass calculations within GBADs or more generally.

⁷ <https://github.com/GBADsInformatics/PPSTheme>

2.2 Methods

In this section we describe a range of methods used to calculate biomass. We first outline the fundamental principles of estimating biomass, before describing a range of methods that can be used in different scenarios of data availability. Different tiers of data granularity are described in Table 2.1. The first method provides a simple approach suitable for global estimates of biomass, with subsequent methods increasing in complexity, accuracy, and data requirements. These more detailed methods can be applied at national and subnational scales. We also discuss the potential for combining methods to increase accuracy and fit for various data qualities.

2.2.1 Estimating livestock biomass

In its simplest form, livestock biomass is calculated as the number of animals multiplied by their liveweight. However, resulting estimates will vary depending on the accuracy and availability of the underlying data, as well as the methods used to estimate livestock population sizes and their liveweight (Bulut & Ivanek, 2022; Callaghan *et al.*, 2021). This guide provides advice on the selection of methodologies based on the type and granularity (level of detail in data structure) of data available.

Biomass of a given livestock population can be calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Biomass (kg)} = N * W \quad (2.1)$$

In which N refers to the total number of animals, and W refers to the *average* liveweight (kg). The ideal scenario would be to have a dataset with the *actual* liveweight (w) of each individual (n) in the population, at a given time, from which the total biomass of the population can be calculated by adding all the w of the n individuals, thus accounting for differences in liveweight within the population (due to breed, age, sex etc).

However, this information rarely exists outside of farm-scale datasets due to the huge investment in time and resources required to individually weigh all the animals in a population, especially since individual liveweights vary over time. Instead, the variables n and w can be estimated to approximate average population biomass.

In this case, the method used to generate these estimates introduces additional sources of systematic and random error. The objective is to minimise systematic errors to the greatest extent possible with the available data, while documenting the uncertainty. This is most often done by disaggregating (breaking down the population data by sub-categories) the population structure (e.g., by animal breed, sex, age class and/or production system) to produce a range of estimated values for n , and the liveweight (w) distribution (instead of a single value) to account for variability of animal liveweights.

2.2.2 Calculation of biomass using average values of liveweight or their proxy

Simple estimates of livestock biomass can be generated by multiplying the number of animals in a population by the average liveweight value, or a proxy value such as slaughter weight (Table 2.2). This approach is suitable for providing initial estimates of biomass, or for high-level estimates at national or global scales where more disaggregated data is not available.

For global analyses or international comparisons, FAOSTAT is a good source of country-level livestock population data (FAO, 1997). Average liveweight and carcass weight for different species are available from the FAO Technical Conversion Factors for Agricultural Commodities (FAO, 2021).

Population and liveweight data derived from FAOSTAT and the FAO Technical Conversion Factors for Agricultural Commodities (FAO, 2021) were also used to calculate the biomass and values of livestock displayed in the GBADs dashboard (<https://gbadske.org/dashboards/biomass/>).

2.2.3 Calculating biomass where number and liveweight of groups of animals are known
Where the number of animals in different subgroups (e.g., animal age and/or sex groups) are known, and the average liveweights of individuals in these groups can be accessed from official statistics or literature, the biomass of a subgroup can be calculated. The biomass of these subgroups can then be combined to get the livestock biomass of the whole population (e.g., Figure 2.1, left side panel).

2.2.4 Calculating biomass where total number is known, but not the population structure
Where information on sizes of subgroups (e.g. sex and/or age groups) is not available, but data on liveweights for these groups are, dynamic population models such as DynMod (Lesnoff, 2008) can be used to model the population structure using data on population dynamics. These values can be estimated via triangulation from the literature (use of a variety of data sources) and other sources including national statistics, survey or case study data, and expert opinion. Meta-analysis can also be used to generate values from literature (LiMayberry *et al.*, 2023). Once the model has been used to estimate population sizes of each age/sex group, biomass is calculated as per section 2.2.3. In addition to sex and age groups, this approach can also be used for production-system or subnational level analysis.

A detailed example of this method can be found in the GBADs Ethiopian case study where the biomass of cattle and small ruminants in the country was estimated (Jemberu *et al.*, 2022; LiMayberry *et al.*, 2023).

2.2.5 Combining subnational estimates of biomass
Where livestock biomass has been calculated for subgroups (such as age and/or sex, or regional groups), the total biomass can be calculated by summing all the subgroups within an area (a state or country), production system or other high-level grouping (Figure 2.1, left side panel). A national value can be calculated by adding all the biomass of subnational regions (Figure 2.1, right side panel). Combination of subgroup estimates (e.g. sub-regions) calculated using data specific to this subgroup, will result in more accurate high-level (e.g. national) estimates, due to the greater granularity of data used.

Figure 2.1 Approaches for estimating total livestock biomass by summing biomass of subgroups within a state (left) and country (right)

2.2.6 Combining different methods to create global estimates of biomass

A coarse estimate of global biomass can be generated using global population data and average liveweight values for each species (e.g., from FAOSTAT, section 2.2.2). However, as highlighted above, the availability and granularity of population and liveweight data varies between countries and production systems so the accuracy of a global estimate can be improved by using country specific data where available. This combined approach is used by the WOA to calculate biomass in order to understand the global use of antimicrobials (Gochez *et al.*, 2019).

2.2.7 Representing uncertainty

When using data to estimate biomass, uncertainties or variations may be associated with the parameters obtained from the data sources described above. Several reasons for uncertainties in these values have been identified, some of which are outlined below.

1. Population values are often estimated by measuring a sample from that population. The value obtained will therefore have a degree of uncertainty attached to it. For example, a survey investigating calf mortality risk in an area in a given year evaluated a sample of 100 calves from a larger population and found four out of 100 calves were dead in the study year. The mortality risk for the year was reported as 4% with a 95% confidence interval (95% CI) of 1.4-9.7%, indicating that the true value of the calf mortality would lie within this range 95% of the time. Wider confidence intervals around an estimate indicates greater uncertainty. When confidence intervals are not given, they can be calculated using the number of deaths and the total population of interest via online tools (e.g., <https://epitools.ausvet.com.au/>).
2. Data may also be reported as a range of possible values rather than a single (point) estimate. For example, a farmer might not know the exact number of livestock they have, or herd size may vary across the year, so they give a range of the herd sizes (e.g., 20-25 sheep).

3. Values reported by different studies in the literature will offer different values for a parameter due to different study areas, sampling strategies, or different target groups of farms.
4. Where little data are available to estimate a parameter (for example, for a specific group or location), the knowledge of experts may be used to fill such data gaps, either through structured expert elicitation methods or less formal communications. However, different experts may give different values, or provide a range of values. To summarise the estimates from these experts, a range of values would be a proper choice. More details on using expert opinions can be found in the literature (Morris, Oakley, & Crowe, 2014; Peters, 2007).

When estimating livestock biomass using parameter values with associated uncertainty, it is important to consider the impacts of these variations on the final biomass estimate. The uncertainty should be addressed when using these values in the calculation and/or modelling of livestock biomass if possible. Deterministic values in the form of single or point estimates can be used to estimate the total biomass quickly. However, a range of the total biomass should be reported wherever possible and the uncertainties in livestock population and liveweight estimates acknowledged.

Ranges of values can be incorporated when estimating total livestock biomass through use of the Monte Carlo simulation (Vose *et al.*, 2001; Vose, 1997) (Figure 2.2). This is a computational technique to model and analyse systems or processes that involve randomness or uncertainty. It can be used to offer not only a point value but also a range of values and enables the estimation of confidence intervals around the final estimate (e.g. total biomass) by combining variations of the input parameters (e.g. population and liveweight). To conduct a Monte Carlo simulation, parameters are defined as distributions. For example, the average liveweight of a cow would be defined as a normal distribution, e.g., the mean value is 300 kg with a standard deviation of 20 kg. Other parameters such as liveweight of other age and/or sex groups, reproductivity, and mortality are also defined as distributions. Multiple iterations are run and for every simulation, a random value is chosen from the defined distribution of the parameter, which are then used for the biomass calculation. A schematic diagram of the Monte Carlo simulation was shown in Figure 2.2. Different biomass values from each simulation can then be summarised to obtain the mean value and its variation. More details about using Monte Carlo simulation can be found in literature (Vose *et al.*, 2001; Vose, 1997).

Figure 2.2 Schematic of a Monte Carlo Simulation for biomass estimation of a cattle population

An example of accounting for uncertainty can be found in the work of LiMayberry *et al.* (2023) who reported that the cattle biomass for the mixed crop livestock system in Ethiopia was 11.3 billion kg (95% CI: 9.8-12.9) in 2021 using a dynamic population model (see Chapter 4, section 4.3.1). This means that the average cattle biomass was 11.3 billion kg, but the true value could vary between 9.8 to 12.9 billion kg due to the uncertainties and variations around the parameters such as population and liveweights of age and/or sex groups, mortality, offtake, reproductivity and others. A sensitivity analysis indicated that better estimations on adult liveweights would improve the accuracy of the cattle biomass estimation in this system. Further discussion of bias and uncertainty can be found in section 2.4.1.

In summary, the quality of the output will depend on the quality of the inputs, the more erroneous the inputs, the bigger the error effects are on the outputs, hence every effort must be made to introduce quality and verified inputs.

2.3 Data requirements

2.3.1 Required data for livestock biomass estimation

This section of the technical guide offers a summary of the data required to estimate the biomass of a given livestock population. The key data required are the number (N) and average liveweight (W) of animals in the target population (Table 2.1).

Table 2.1 Data requirements and possible data sources for estimating livestock biomass

Data required	Details	Possible data sources
Number of animals in a given population	<p>Disaggregated by breed, sex, and age where possible.</p> <p>Where data on population structure is not available, known values of mortality, reproduction, and offtake rates (proportions of animals sold or consumed per year) can be input into dynamic population models (in which the livestock population would change over time) to estimate the number of animals within each age/sex group.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National statistics (e.g., livestock census data) FAOSTAT (FAO 1997)
Average liveweight (kg) for a type of animal	<p>Disaggregated by breed, sex, and age where possible.</p> <p>Where liveweight data is not available, slaughter weight, carcass weight or livestock units may be used as a proxy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National statistics FAOSTAT (FAO, 1997) FAO Domestic Animal Diversity Information System (FAO, 2022) FAO technical conversion factors (FAO, 2021) Survey data Industry or market data Literature (including primary research articles, reviews, meta-analyses, project reports) Expert opinion

Average liveweight of species are often not included in the official statistics, and the use of proxy data such as slaughter weight, carcass weight or livestock units (the weight of a typical animal used to compare across species) may be required. However, there are advantages and disadvantages of using these proxy values (Table 2.2), and the potential bias should be considered.

Table 2.2. Proxy values for estimating an average liveweight of a species

Parameter/data	Calculation notes	Advantages	Disadvantages
Slaughter weight	Slaughter weight is substituted for liveweight in biomass calculation	Slaughter weights may be more available than average liveweights because weight is recorded at slaughter	Slaughter weight will not be representative of a population
Carcass weight	Carcass weight divided by dressing percentage (i.e. the proportion of liveweight that is retained once the carcass is processed)	Carcass weights may be more available than average liveweights	Carcass weight will not be representative of a population
Livestock units	Conversion ratios of species multiplied by assumed weight of one unit. See Table 4 in appendix for examples.	Simple to use. May already be used by local industry or governments.	Often regionally specific. Calculations are based on energy requirements & utilisation. Can introduce large errors.

2.3.2 Selecting data for biomass estimation

While the required data is ideally disaggregated by animal breed, sex, age, and production system as mentioned above, in some cases, only national-level estimates may be available. Different data sources for livestock populations and liveweights have different granularities. For example, livestock populations from FAOSTAT (FAO, 1997) are aggregated by country and species but do not have population data disaggregated by breed. In comparison, in nationally collected statistics from Ethiopia, population data for different breeds and age groups are available (Central Statistical Agency of Ethiopia, 2021). The granularity of available data can be classified into three tiers, with Tier 3 the most accurate and Tier 1 the least accurate (Table 2.3).

Table 2.3. Tiers of data granularity for calculating livestock biomass

	Details	Population data	Liveweight data
Tier 3	Most accurate. Data comes from local sources, and estimates are available at subnational levels.	Number of animals by sex, age, and/or breed Number of animals within a state, zone, region, or production system	Liveweight of animals by sex, age, and/or breed
Tier 2	Data is available at a national level.	Total national population	Country-specific estimates of liveweight
Tier 1	Least accurate but easily scalable to a global level. Data is based on global or regional databases.	Total national population	Liveweight values are not country-specific

As highlighted above (Table 2.1), data used to estimate livestock biomass can come from different sources, including official reports, surveys, literature, expert opinions, etc. Not all data sources are equally reliable, and several factors should be considered, including:

- Are the values from trusted sources, e.g., reputable institutions, peer-reviewed publications, or practitioners who are recognised experts in their fields?
- Are the values representative of the target region or production system?
- Were proper statistical methods used to design the sampling frame?

2.4 Interpretation of outputs

This guide has introduced a series of approaches for estimating livestock biomass at different scales (global, regional, national, and subnational), for different sub-groups (e.g. sex and age groups), and with different data granularities. The outputs of these methods could be used for a variety of purposes, allowing for comparison of livestock biomass by species, country, sub-group and year.

An example of a potential output can be seen in Figure 2.3, which shows the breakdown of total biomass, at a global scale, by livestock species. Cattle contribute most to global livestock biomass, followed by chickens, pigs, buffaloes, sheep, and goats. In addition, this figure shows the increasing trend in total biomass over time. Using this guide, similar analysis could be carried out at national or subnational level.

Figure 2.3 Global livestock Biomass from 2000 to 2019 using the slaughter weight and population data from FAOstat (FAO, 1997).

Comparison of biomass of a given species between different production systems may assist in understanding local food security. For example, using a population dynamic model, Jemberu *et al.* (2022) estimated that sheep biomass in the mixed crop-livestock and pastoral systems in Ethiopia in 2021 were 595 and 454 million kg, respectively. In comparison, goat biomass was 409 million kg in mixed crop-livestock systems and 671 million kg in pastoral systems. These results showed that sheep in the mixed crop-livestock system were contributing more biomass than the sheep in the pastoral system, while the opposite was true for goats. Such information can inform decision makers about the relative importance of each species in a production system, and their demand for resources (e.g., feed, veterinary services).

Livestock biomass can also be used as the denominator for animal health loss analysis so users can compare disease burdens between different livestock sectors (see Chapter 4). For example, Figure 2.4 illustrates the burden of animal disease for cattle in Ethiopia by state. When expressed as an absolute value, the burden of disease is highest in the central regions of Oromia and Amhara (Figure 2.4a). However, expressing the burden of disease per unit of livestock biomass indicates a relatively higher burden in the pastoral regions of Afar and Somali (Figure 2.4b).

Figure 2.4 State-level estimates of the Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE) in Ethiopian cattle by a) total value, and b) per kg biomass (right) (Images captured from GBADs Burden of animal diseases in [Ethiopia dashboard](#))

2.4.1 Considerations around bias and uncertainty

Bias can be introduced when using a proxy for the liveweight of livestock where these data are not available. For example, the TLU conversion ratio is based on the metabolic energy requirements of different livestock in low-input production systems of Africa. Although it has been used elsewhere to estimate animal biomass, it is not the most reliable method because it doesn't account for regional differences in species, herd structures, and production systems. Rothman-Ostrow *et al.* (2020) found that using TLU would lead to an underestimate of livestock biomass in some countries. Similarly, where data on liveweight are not available, country-specific data on average slaughter weight may be used as a proxy. However, it should be noted that this approach introduces additional errors since slaughtered animals are probably not representative of the broader population. Firstly, the slaughtered animals are mainly adult animals in most countries. The age and/or sex structure of the slaughtered animal group may differ from that of the same species on the farm. Secondly, the body conditions may vary between slaughtered animals and animals on a farm. For example, slaughtered beef cattle from intensive commercial farms in the UK would be heavier than the average beef cattle in the same country. In comparison, slaughtered cattle in Ethiopia are mainly the old cattle from small herds, and the body condition of the old cattle is often not as good as the young and healthy cattle on a farm. Given that the source of slaughtered animals varies between countries, using slaughter weight as the average liveweight of a species would introduce positive or negative bias in estimating livestock biomass for different countries.

2.5 Summary

This chapter of the GBADs Technical Guide offers practical guidance for the estimation of livestock biomass at the current point in time (2024). There are different methods to estimate livestock biomass and users should select a proper method and required data based on the study question, and data and resource availability. Variations around input parameters and ranges of estimated biomass outputs should be considered and presented where possible.

The GBADs methods presented in this guide may be developed and refined over time. Updates to GBADs methodologies will be added to the living guides in future versions and the reader is encouraged to consult the GBADs website for publications on this topic as they become available (<https://animalhealthmetrics.org/publications/>)

2.6 References

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2.7 Biomass: Appendix

Table 2.4 Summary of commonly used Livestock Units. Note that the equivalence of most livestock units is based on the energy requirements of livestock, not just liveweight.

Livestock Unit	Country/region of use	Equivalence	Reference
Adult equivalent (AE)	Australia	A 2.25-year-old, 450 kg <i>Bos taurus</i> steer (castrated male) walking 7 km/day with zero weight change	(McLennan <i>et al.</i> , 2020)
Animal Units (AU)	USA	1000 lb mature cow and her suckling calf	(Redfearn & Bidwell, 2017)
Dry sheep equivalent (DSE)	Australia	50 kg, 2-year-old merino wether (castrated male) at maintenance	(The NSW Department of Primary Industries, 2023)
Livestock Unit (LSU)	Europe, UK	650 kg adult dairy cow producing 3000 kg milk annually, without additional concentrated foodstuffs	(Eurostat, 2023)
Large Stock Unit (LSU)	South Africa	450 kg ox (mature castrated male) with a weight gain of 0.5 kg/day on grass pasture	(Mokolobate <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Standard Pig Units (SPU)	Australia	Pig equivalent to a grower pig (average weight 40 kg) based on volatile solids production in manure	(McGahan <i>et al.</i> , 2001)
Stock Unit (SU)	New Zealand	55 kg empty (non-pregnant) ewe	(Parker, 1998)
Tropical Livestock Unit (TLU)	Tropical Africa. May also be applied to other low- and middle-income countries	A 250 kg camel	(Jahnke, 1982)

Chapter 3 Estimating the economic value of farmed animals

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Abstract

An understanding of the economic value of farmed animals is important as a baseline for making decisions about the future of farmed animal production, including decisions about managing the risks due to animal diseases and making investments in risk mitigation policies and strategies. The purpose of this technical guide is to a) describe the economic value framework within which farmed animals can be valued, and b) describe methodologies to calculate the economic value of farmed animals and outline the data required. Examples, including an R code, that demonstrate how to calculate the economic value of farmed animals are provided. These can be adapted by the user to their individual analysis context. It is anticipated that this guide will be useful for researchers, livestock production system analysts, policy-makers and other stakeholders who may be interested in this topic. The document is intended to guide the user in undertaking their own economic value assessment of farmed animals. The guide can be used for assessments at various geographical scales and for a variety of different foci/contexts and timeframes.

¹ [GBADS – Global Burden of Animal Diseases \(animalhealthmetrics.org\)](https://animalhealthmetrics.org/)

3.1 Introduction

The current chapter of the GBADs Technical Guide (version 1.0) focuses on ways of estimating the economic value of farmed animals. This includes terrestrial animals such as cattle, pigs, sheep, chickens, goats, horses, mules and buffalos, and aquatic animals such as prawns, tilapia, oysters, and mussels. Within the analytical structure of GBADs, the estimation of the economic value of farmed animals is categorised under ‘Livestock populations – Economic investment in animals and infrastructure’ (Figure 1.1).

An improved understanding of the economic value of farmed animals and how it varies between production systems, between countries, and across time, can offer a baseline for discussions about future production systems and market development. It also aids discussions about investments into animal health and welfare, the insurance value of farmed animals, environmental impacts of livestock production (e.g. greenhouse gas emissions), the importance of livestock for livelihoods, and trade-offs (Schrobback *et al.*, 2023).

In this chapter we a) describe the economic value framework within which farmed animals can be valued, and b) describe methodologies to calculate the economic value of farmed animals and outline the data required (examples that demonstrate how to undertake the calculation are also provided). The document is intended to guide the user in undertaking their own economic value assessment of farmed animals. The guide can be used for assessments at various geographical scales and for different foci/contexts and timeframes.

This technical guide is based on work published by Schrobback *et al.* (2023), which can be freely accessed under following link: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2023.100722>. The reader is highly encouraged to familiarise themselves with this work alongside using the guidance in this chapter.

This chapter includes links to the R code and associated documentation which was used by Schrobback *et al.* (2023) to estimate the global economic value of farmed animals. This code is provided as an example which can be adapted by the user to their individual analysis context.

Studies that have adopted the outlined methodologies within a national livestock assessment context include; Jemberu *et al.* (2022) for small ruminants in Ethiopia, LiMayberryJemberuSchrobbackHerreroChatersKnight Jones *et al.* (2023) for cattle in Ethiopia, Smith *et al.* (2024) for livestock in Indonesia, and Asteraye *et al.* (2024) for equids in Ethiopia. Users are encouraged to refer to these publications as examples.

The methodologies presented here could also be adapted to wild animals and farmed game. However, case studies that focus on the economic value of these animal categories have not yet been conducted under the GBADs programme.

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows. Sections 3.1.1 to 3.1.3 provides an overview of the concept of the total economic value and why it is currently only possible to estimate the direct use value which farmed animals provide society and not of other value types, e.g. indirect use value, option value, non-market value. Section 3.2 outlines the methodologies and data requirements and provides examples for calculating the economic value of farmed animals. Section 3.3 offers suggestions on the interpretation of estimates and their usability, and, finally, Section 3.4 provides a summary of this guide.

3.1.1 Approach to estimating the economic value of farmed animals

Economic value is a complex concept which is not the same as the concept of price. The concept of value is defined as the weighting or importance that individuals place on something, e.g. a good or

service, which reflects the utility/benefit that they gain from it (Viner, 1925). In contrast, the price of a good or service is its monetary value, which is derived from its demand and supply in the market in which it is traded (Hubbard, 2015). For some goods or services there are no tangible markets and subsequently no prices, but individuals/society still value them. For example, there are no markets for air quality but society values high air quality. The price of a good or service that individuals may be willing to pay is typically reflected in the value that they place on that good or service, but this value may also transcend the price that they pay for it.

To illustrate the different types of value that farmed animals can hold for individuals and society, the concept of the Total Economic Value (TEV) of farmed animals will be described in this section. This sets out the types of economic values, namely the value of live animals and the value of primary/secondary outputs, for which methodologies are currently available and for which estimates can be derived relative straightforwardly. This section also describes value types for which there are currently only a limited number of methodologies. This section provides a rationale for estimating the economic value of farmed animals at different scales, e.g. global, continental, national, regional or farm level. Analysts need to be aware of the different value types before conducting their analysis.

3.1.2 The Total Economic Value framework

The TEV is a conceptual framework that aims to capture the complete economic benefits that farmed animals contribute to human society (Schrobback *et al.*, 2023) (Figure 3.1). This framework is the guiding principle for the economic value estimation of farmed animals in this technical guide. The TEV concept is used in other contexts as well, e.g. environmental cost–benefit analysis (e.g., Bateman *et al.*, 2002).

Total economic value is categorised into *use values* and *non-use values*. The *use value* of farmed animals refers to the benefits that individuals or society derive from direct interactions with animals, animal products and the services that animals provide (Schrobback *et al.*, 2023). *Use values* can be distinguished further into direct use, indirect use, and option values (Figure 3.1).

The *direct use value* of farmed animals is the economic value that can be derived from the consumptive use or utilisation of animals. Direct use values include the value of a) live animals that are traded in markets at a market price, b) the primary and secondary outputs that animals generate, e.g. meat, milk, eggs, skins/hides, wool, manure, and c) the services provided by animals, e.g. transportation, draught power, insurance and financial services (collateral for loans, financial security, livelihood protection) (Schrobback *et al.*, 2023).

Indirect use values are the benefits derived from the non-consumptive use of the products and services that farmed animals provide, e.g. maintaining cultural, traditional and religious values (rituals, ceremonial/sacrificial offerings, symbol for social status) and landscapes (grazing to reduce fire risk or control invasive weeds - a service that is not traded in markets) (Davies *et al.*, 2022; Martin-Collado *et al.*, 2014; Schrobback *et al.*, 2023; Szűcs *et al.*, 2012).

The *option value* of farmed animals is understood to be the value that individuals or society place on having the option to use animals in future. For example, they may wish to use the animals for breeding in the future, and so existing livestock are valued because they constitute the genetic breeding pool for future animal production (e.g., Drucker *et al.*, 2001; Zander *et al.*, 2013).

The *non-use value* of farmed animals are understood to be the intrinsic or passive values that animals offer individuals or society (Schrobback *et al.*, 2023). This value category can be further differentiated into *bequest value*, *altruistic value*, and *existence value*.

The *bequest value* is the value the current generation places on ensuring that future generations will be able to derive use and non-use from farmed animals (Schrobback *et al.*, 2023). The *altruistic value* of farmed animals is the value that an individual or society places on ensuring that farmed animals are available for the use by other individuals or societies, even if they themselves do not use or benefit from them (Schrobback *et al.*, 2023). The *existence value* of farmed animals is the value gained from simply knowing that these animals exist; it is the benefit that farmed animals afford to individuals or society irrespective of whether they, or others, currently use the animals or plan to use them in the future (Schrobback *et al.*, 2023).

The existence of non-use values of farmed animals has been highlighted in several studies, most of which focus on livestock in pastoral and traditional production systems (e.g., Gandini & Villa, 2003; Marsoner *et al.*, 2018; Moll, 2005). However, at this stage, there are only a limited number of empirical studies that quantify these non-use values (e.g., Bennison *et al.*, 1997; Hansson & Lagerkvist, 2015).

Figure 3.1 Total Economic Value (TEV) of farmed animals.

Source: Adapted from Schrobback et al. (2023). Notes: FA: farmed animals. Dashed boxes indicate the economic value types that have been estimated for farmed animals in Ethiopia and Indonesia, e.g. Jemberu et al. (2022), Li et al. (2023), Smith et al. (2024) and Asteraye et al. (2024). These studies serve as proof of concept for the programme and will act as a springboard for its global implementation. This figure was originally published under copyright licence CC BY 4.0 DEED Attribution 4.0 International (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Within GBADs, the development of methodologies to estimate the economic value of farmed animals has focused solely on live animals and primary and secondary outputs. Therefore, the remainder of this technical guide only provides methodologies and data requirements for estimating these types of economic value. The third type of economic value, i.e. the value of the services animals provide (e.g. draught power), has not been included, as there has been no theoretical assessment of how these different types of values can be added without double counting the value of live animals. The GBADs programme has, however, undertaken a study estimating the value of the transportation and draught power provided by equids (Asteraye *et al.*, 2024), and users of the current guide are encouraged to adopt this methodology to undertake separate assessments of the value of services provided by livestock.

The focus on the consumptive use/utilisation value of live animals and animal products differentiates animal's direct use value from other value types in the TEV framework. The demand and supply in markets generates a market price which reflects the direct use value of live animals and their products that sellers and buyers agreed on. Therefore, the market price is a key variable for the estimation of the direct use value of farmed animals, which will be outlined in more detail in section 3.2. Hence, the economic value estimation within this guide will follow the principles of a market-based approach, i.e. using market information such as prices and quantities to value farmed animals.

For the estimation of the direct use value, live animals are considered as assets, which are defined as resources that are controlled by entities (such as smallholders, businesses, countries) because of past events (e.g. inputs to production), based on which, future benefits are expected to be received by those entities (Petzke, 1998; Schrobback *et al.*, 2023). In the remainder of this chapter, the term assets is used to refer to live animals. No other farm assets/liabilities will be considered.

The user of this guide will notice that the direct use value is only one part of the TEV that farmed animals generate (dashed boxes in Figure 3.1). This should be considered in any type of economic value analysis for farmed animals. The remainder of this chapter will use the term economic value as a synonym for the direct use value of farmed animals.

3.1.3 Estimating the economic value of farmed animals using different scales, foci and timeframes

The guide presented in this chapter is intended to assist users in undertaking their own economic value estimations of farmed animals, and it can be used at different geographical scales, i.e. global, continental, country, group-of-country, regional/district, or farm level. Similarly, it can be used for estimations in different contexts, e.g. comparison of different livestock groups or productions systems, and for estimations at a particular point in time or over multiple years. The scale, focus, and timeframe of an economic value analysis will be determined by the availability of data and by what the analyst wants to achieve in undertaking the assessment (e.g. meet a particular need, achieve certain goals).

For example, Schrobback *et al.* (2023) used the global analysis scale to estimate the economic value of terrestrial and aquatic farmed animals, covering 181 countries and multiple years. The results offered global economic value patterns for various livestock categories, e.g. cattle, pigs, chickens, goats, sheep, and aquatic animal categories. These authors identified animal groups that generate a high economic value relative to other animal groups. Schrobback *et al.* (2023) also illustrated the global distribution of livestock value, highlighting their importance for livelihoods, specifically in lower-income countries. Such findings may be of interest for global decision-making about the future development of the farmed animal sector.

Smith *et al.* (2024) demonstrated that an economic value analysis can also be conducted at a national scale. An analysis at continental or group-of-country scale, e.g. European Union (EU) can also be conducted.

A subnational analysis can assess the economic value of farmed animals for a specific district/region or for several districts and regions within a country. Results from such analysis can provide patterns in the distribution of the economic value that farmed animals generate across a country. This may offer information for decision-makers to evaluate production systems and direct investment into priority districts/regions based on their relative importance to national or provincial economies. Examples of this approach include the work conducted by Jemberu *et al.* (2022) and Li *et al.* (2023) on livestock production systems in Ethiopia, and the work undertaken by Smith *et al.* (2024) on key livestock species in Indonesia.

Economic analyses at farm scale are typically conducted for commercial purposes, such as farm stock-taking or asset valuation, which may include comparison of breed asset values.

Analysts may also consider conducting economic valuations of farmed animals across time, since the monetary value (price) is a dynamic concept, meaning it changes over time for various reasons, e.g. supply and demand in markets, production input availability and costs, government regulations, technical innovation. An analysis focusing on economic value estimation over time, e.g. a 10-year production timeframe, can produce useful information about trends in the economic value of farmed animals.

Data requirements and methodologies that may be considered for an economic value analysis of farmed animals will be described in the following section.

3.2 Data requirements and methodologies

3.2.1 Overview

This section outlines the data requirements and methodologies to estimate the economic value of a) live animals that are traded in markets, and b) the primary and secondary outputs that animals generate and that are traded in markets, e.g. meat, milk, eggs, skins/hides, wool, manure (see Figure 3.1).

The estimation of the economic value of farmed animals requires several types of key data, including:

- Prices*: The current market selling prices for live animals and primary/secondary products.
- Quantities*: The livestock/aquaculture population or number of heads/animals, kilograms/tonnes of primary/secondary products.
- Liveweight conversion factors*: The measures that can be used to convert the quantity of animals into a liveweight equivalent.

More detailed information about the data requirements will be outlined in Section 3.2.2.

The methodologies to estimate the economic value of live animals and the primary/secondary products that they produce consist of three components:

- Asset value*: The monetary value of assets (live farmed animals). It refers to the price and quantity at which they are traded in a market at a specific point in time.
- Output value*: The monetary value of primary outputs (meat, milk, eggs) and secondary outputs (manure, hides, wool, etc.). It refers to the price and quantity at which they are traded at a market at a specific point in time.
- Combined asset and output value*: The sum of asset and output values.

The relationship between asset and output values is conceptually illustrated in Figure 3.2. Details about the calculation of the asset value, output value and combined asset and output value, including potential issues of double counting, is provided in Sections 3.2.3 to 3.2.5.

Figure 3.2 Conceptual illustration of the components of economic value.

3.2.2 Data requirements

Before attempting to undertake an analysis of the economic value of farmed animals, the analyst needs to clearly define the scope of the assessment, which includes the geographical scale,

focus/context, and timeframe (see Section 3.1.3). The analyst can then identify relevant data that can be used for the analysis.

An overview of the key data types and potential data sources for the analysis of asset values and output values at different geographical scales is presented in Table 3.1 (non-exhaustive list, examples only). The analyst is highly encouraged to identify data that best suits the geographical scale, focus/context, and timeframe of their analysis, e.g. data that is easily accessible, comprehensive, and reliable. Information from different data sources should always be assessed critically, e.g. validation through experts and common sense, before the data is used for analysis.

3.2.2.1 Asset value data requirements

An estimation of asset values requires data on the *quantity of animals*, which is the total livestock/aquaculture population or number of heads in a herd. Data for the quantity of animals may need to be available disaggregated by livestock/aquaculture category, age, breed, and sex depending on the focus of the analysis. Time series data may be needed.

For the different analysis scales, there are different potential options for data sources. For example, global livestock population data can be obtained from the corporate statistical database of the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (hereafter FAOSTAT) (FAO, 2021)¹. The national statistics available through FAOSTAT are not broken down by age group, sex or breed, but this information may be available from other data sources, e.g. annual farm surveys conducted by a country's bureau of statistics, national livestock/aquaculture industry associations, or representative farms. For example, at national scale, data may be available from annual farm surveys conducted by a country's bureau of statistics, national livestock/aquaculture industry associations or from representative farms. Data on the quantity of farmed animals that were affected by various diseases can be obtained from the World Animal Health Organisation via its World Animal Health Information System (WAHIS) (WAHIS, 2023), which provides data on the numbers of susceptible animals, vaccinated animals, and animal deaths. This data can be used to calculate the economic burden value of animal diseases at national or larger geographical scale.

There is currently no database that provides information about global aquatic farmed animal populations; FAO's global fishery and aquaculture database, Fishstat (FAO, 2024), only offers data about fish products/outputs (and biomass conversion factors for a small number of fish species).

If price data for live animals is only available as a weight-based unit, e.g. USD/tonnes/year instead of USD/quantity of animals/year, it will be necessary to use liveweight conversion factors to convert the quantity of animals into a liveweight equivalent (also referred to as livestock biomass). The use of a common (weight-based) unit is beneficial for economic value comparisons across different livestock/aquaculture categories. Detailed information about livestock biomass conversion approaches can be found in chapter 2 Estimating livestock biomass. The FAO's *Technical Conversion Factors (TCFs) for Agricultural Commodities* (FAO, 2021) provides data on country-specific biomass conversion factors. However, national or subnational data from a country's bureau of statistics, national livestock/aquaculture industry associations or from representative farms may also exist, and these can provide more detailed information on liveweight, e.g. by age, breed, and sex. It should also be noted that the use of different biomass conversion factors will lead to different asset values, the same applies to other data types.

¹ <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data> (For quantity data, select the crops and livestock products database, e.g. product quantity, livestock processed, for price data select producer prices database, e.g. producer price (USD/tonne), items)

For data on *prices of live animals*, the analyst should consider using the current market selling prices of animals at a specific point in time, e.g. the price at the time when an animal was sold at a market or the average farm gate price within a specific timeframe. This price reflects the current market value of animals (Schrobback, 2024). Potential data sources for current market selling prices include FAOSTAT (global scale), Eurostat² (group-of-country scale), a country's bureau of statistics, national livestock/aquaculture industry associations and representative farms.

It should be noted that current market selling prices for assets may not always be available and that alternative livestock valuation/pricing methods may need to be considered, e.g. historical/acquisition costs and cost of production (Petzke, 1998). Schrobback (2024) provides an overview of alternative livestock valuation methods, their advantages/disadvantages, and their data requirements.

² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/data/statistical-themes#agriculture-fisheries>

Table 3.1: Data requirements and potential data sources for estimating the asset value and output value of farmed animals.

Required data types	Definition	Possible data sources by assessment scale			
		Global	Continental/ Group of countries	National	Regional/Farm
Asset value estimation					
Quantity of animals	Total livestock/aquaculture population or number of heads [^]	FAOSTAT ¹ , WAHIS ²	FAOSTAT, WAHIS, Eurostat (EU) ³	FAOSTAT, WAHIS, Eurostat (EU), national bureau of statistics	Livestock/aquaculture industry associations, representative farms
Liveweight conversion factors	Factors/measures that can be used to convert the quantity of animals into a standardised liveweight equivalent [^]	FAO TCFs ⁴	FAO TCFs	FAO TCFs, national bureau of statistics	Livestock/aquaculture industry associations, local markets and slaughterhouses, representative farms
Prices of live animals	Current market selling prices or farm gate prices for livestock and aquatic farmed animals [^]	FAOSTAT, The World Bank ^{5*}	FAOSTAT, Eurostat (EU), The World Bank*, national bureau of statistics [#]	FAOSTAT, Eurostat (EU), national statistics/market, indemnity programmes, national bureau of statistics [#]	Livestock/aquaculture industry associations, local markets, livestock marketing companies (agents/brokers), slaughterhouses, representative farms, national bureau of statistics [#]
Output value estimation					
Quantity of primary/secondary products	Total weight or volume of primary/secondary products, e.g. meat, milk, eggs, manure, hides, wool, etc.	FAOSTAT, FAO FishStat ⁶	FAOSTAT, FAO FishStat, Eurostat (EU)	FAOSTAT, FAO FishStat, Eurostat (EU), national bureau of statistics	Livestock/aquaculture industry associations, representative farms
Prices of primary/secondary products	Current market selling prices or farm gate prices for primary/secondary products	FAOSTAT, FAO FishStat, The World Bank*	FAOSTAT, FAO FishStat, Eurostat (EU), The World Bank*, national bureau of statistics [#]	FAOSTAT, FAO FishStat, Eurostat (EU), national statistics/markets, national bureau of statistics [#]	Livestock/aquaculture industry associations, local markets, cooperatives, product marketing companies (agents/brokers), representative farms, national bureau of statistics [#]

Source: Adapted from Schrobback (2024). [^] Depending on the analysis focus, the data may need to be disaggregated by livestock/aquaculture category, age, breed, sex. Time series data for these parameters may be needed. * PPP conversion rates for cross-country price comparisons. # Price index for inflation adjustment when using time series data.

¹ <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data> (For quantity data, select the crops and livestock products database in the 'Production' section, followed by the element e.g. 'production quantity', and item, e.g. 'livestock processed', that you are interested in. For price data, select the producer prices database in the 'Prices' section, followed by the element, e.g. 'producer price (USD/tonne)', and item, e.g. cattle meat); ² <https://wahis.woah.org/#/home>; ³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/data/statistical-themes#agriculture-fisheries>;

⁴ <https://www.fao.org/economic/the-statistics-division-ess/methodology/methodology-systems/technical-conversion-factors-for-agricultural-commodities/en/>;

⁵ <https://databank.worldbank.org/databases/ppp>; ⁶ <https://www.fao.org/fishery/en/fishstat>

3.2.2.2 Output value data requirements

The estimation of the output (offtake) value requires data on *quantities of primary and secondary products*, i.e. the total weight or volume of the products that are generated by the assets. For an analysis at global scale, FAOSTAT data can be used for livestock products. FAO FishStat provides information on quantities of products produced from aquatic farmed animals. National data sources may also provide the quantity data needed to estimate the output value (see Table 3.1).

The second type of data required to estimate output value are *prices for primary/secondary products*, that is, the current market selling prices or farm gate prices for primary/secondary products. This type of data can be obtained from the same sources that offer data on quantities of primary/secondary products and from the World Bank, product marketing companies and national bureaux of statistics (Table 3.1). However, analysts should be aware that data sources for the estimation of asset value and output value may not always be the same.

3.2.2.3 Adjusting price data

The current market value of assets and outputs is a dynamic value; hence it should be assessed periodically to ensure that the latest values are integrated into any analysis. The adjustment of price data for inflation, using the general price index, needs to be considered by the analyst for assessments that focus on comparing economic values over time. Information about how to conduct inflation adjustments is provided in Appendix A (section 0). Price index data is country-specific information and may be provided specifically for livestock and food products (meat, milk, eggs), depending on the country. Data about price indices is typically available from a country's national bureau of statistics or the national reserve bank.

For analyses that compare economic values across countries that do not have the same currency, analysts need to adjust the price data to account for purchasing power parity (PPP), otherwise the derived economic values are not directly comparable. PPPs are the rates of currency conversion that can be used to equalise the purchasing power of different currencies, by eliminating the differences in price levels between countries. Information about how to conduct a PPP adjustment is provided in Appendix B (section 3.7). PPP data is available from The World Bank¹.

A description of the methodologies to estimate the asset value, output value and combined asset and output value is provided in the following sections.

3.2.3 Methodology for calculating the asset value

The asset value is here considered as the monetary value of live farmed animals or, more specifically, the value at which they are traded in a market at a specific point in time. The asset value of farmed animals can be estimated by multiplying the quantity of animals (total livestock/aquaculture population or number of heads) by the prices of live animals (current market selling prices or farm gate prices). This can be expressed as follows:

$$\text{Asset value} = \text{Quantity of animals} * \text{Price of animals} \quad (3.1)$$

Depending on the scale and focus of the analysis, it may be preferable to first carry out separate calculations for different subgroups of animals (e.g. divided by country, livestock category, age, sex, breed group) and then add the subtotals together (see details in Schrobback *et al.*, 2023). Price adjustments may also be required (see Appendix A (section 0) and Appendix B (section 3.7)).

¹ https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/icp/brief/Sources_of_PPPs

A conversion from the quantity of animals (heads) to liveweight equivalents using biomass conversion factors may be needed if price data for assets is only available as price per tonne. Accounting for biomass conversion, the asset value can be calculated as following:

$$\text{Asset value} = (\text{Quantity of animals} * \text{Biomass conversion factor}) * \text{Price per tonne} \quad (3.2)$$

The following example provides details on how the asset value can be calculated. The example focuses on cattle in Australia for 2015.

Calculating the asset value of cattle in Australia (2015)*Data for calculating the asset value of cattle in Australia in 2015:*

Data	Data source
No. of cattle: 27,412,872 heads	FAO (2021), Data, Production, 'Crops and Livestock Products' database - Country: Australia, Item: Live animals, Element: Stocks, Year: 2015
Producer cattle price: 1,185 USD/tonne liveweight	FAO (2021), Data, Prices, 'Producer Prices' database - Country: Australia, Item: Meat liveweight, cattle, Element: Producer Price (USD/tonne), Year: 2015, Months: Annual value
Heads of cattle slaughtered: 10,103,100	FAO (2021), Data, Production, 'Crops and Livestock Products' database - Country: Australia, Item: Livestock primary, Element: Producing Animals/Slaughtered & Production Quantity, Year: 2015
Production quantity: 2,661,640 tonnes of meat	
FAO biomass conversion factor - Carcass weight as a % of liveweight in Australia: 50%	FAO (2021) -Country: Australia, Livestock products: Cattle
Liveweight biomass conversion factor for beef cattle in Australia: 380kg	Commonwealth of Australia (2023); Jahnke (1982)

Equation:

$$\text{Asset value} = (\text{Quantity of animals} * \text{Biomass conversion factor}) * \text{Price per tonne}$$

Case 1: Calculating the asset value using FAO's biomass conversion factor (carcass weight)

Asset value of live cattle in Australian in 2015 = 27,412,872 [heads] x (2,661,640 [meat production quantity tonnes]/10,103,100 [heads slaughtered]) x (1/0.5 [carcass conversion factor]) x 1,185 [meat price in USD/tonne] = USD 17,112,704,685.

Case 2: Calculating the asset value using liveweight biomass

Asset value of live cattle in Australia in 2015 = 27,412,872 [heads] x (380kg/1,000) [liveweight converted to tonnes] x 1,185 [meat price in USD/tonne] = USD 12,344,016,262.

The two examples demonstrate that the use of different biomass conversion factors can lead to different asset values.

3.2.4 Methodology for calculating the output value

The output value is the monetary value at which primary outputs (meat, milk, eggs) and secondary outputs (manure, hides, wool, etc.) from farmed animals are traded in a market at a specific point in time. The output value can be estimated by multiplying the quantity of primary/secondary products by the prices of these products (current market selling prices). This can be expressed as following:

$$\text{Output value} = \text{Quantity of products} * \text{Price of products} \quad (3.3)$$

The unit of the quantity of outputs should be the same across all primary/secondary products that are included in the analysis, e.g. tonnes. As for the asset value, the output values may be derived first by product type and then added up over all products over the scale, contexts, and timeframes of the analysis. Price adjustments may be required (see Appendix A (section 0 and Appendix B (section 3.7)). Detailed information on how to calculate the output value is provided by Schrobback *et al.* (2023).

The following example provides details on how the output value can be calculated. The example focuses on cattle meat in Australia for 2015.

Calculating the output value of cattle meat in Australia (2015)

Data for calculating the output value of cattle in Australia in 2015:

Data	Data source
Quantity of cattle meat produced: 2,661,640 tonnes	FAO (2021), Data, Production 'Crops and livestock products' database - Country: Australia, Item: Livestock processes - Meat of cattle with bone, fresh or chilled, Element: Production quantity, Year: 2015
Producer price: USD 1,185.5 per tonne	FAO (2021), Data, Production 'Producer prices' database - Country: Australia, Item: Meat of cattle with bone, fresh or chilled, Element: Producer price (USD/tonne), Year: 2015, Months: Annual value

Equation:

$$\text{Output value} = \text{Quantity of products} * \text{Price of products}$$

Case 3: Calculation of output value

Output value of cattle meat in Australia in 2015 = 2,661,640 tonnes x 1,185.5 USD/tonne = USD 3,155,374,220.

The results shows that the output value of cattle meat in Australia in 2015 appeared to be significantly lower (USD 3.16 billion) than the asset value of cattle (USD 17.11 billion or USD 12.34 billion, depending on which biomass conversion factor was used in the calculation, see example in Section 3.3).

3.2.5 Methodology for combining asset and output value

The combined asset and output value is derived by adding up both economic value types as follows:

$$\text{Combined asset and output value} = \text{Asset value (3.2)} + \text{Output value (3.3)} \quad 3.4$$

This relationship is illustrated in Figure 3.2. The following example provides details on how the combined asset and output value can be calculated. As above, the example focuses on live cattle and cattle meat in Australia for 2015; it uses the asset values and output values derived in the examples above.

Calculating the combined asset and output value of cattle and cattle meat in Australia (2015)

Data for calculating the combined asset and output value of cattle in Australia in 2015:

Data	Source
Asset value (1) = USD 17,112,704,685	Case 1 (see above)
Asset value (2) = USD 12,344,016,262	Case 2 (see above)
Output value = USD 3,155,374,220	Case 3 (see above)

Equation:

$$\text{Combined asset and output value} = \text{Asset value} + \text{Output value}$$

Case 4: Calculation of the combined asset value (Case 1) and output value:

$$\text{Combined value (1)} = \text{USD } 17,112,704,685 + \text{USD } 3,155,374,220 = \text{USD } 20,268,078,905$$

Case 5: Calculation of the combined asset value (Case 2) and output value:

$$\text{Combined value (1)} = \text{USD } 12,344,016,262 + \text{USD } 3,155,374,220 = \text{USD } 15,499,390,482$$

The results show that the combined asset and output value can be affected by variability in either component of the equation. In such cases, the analyst should consider conducting a sensitivity analysis and, depending on availability, using other data sources that may help in deriving more robust results.

3.2.6 Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis can help to determine how different data for the key variables, e.g. quantity and price data and biomass conversion factors, may affect the results (see examples above). A sensitivity analysis can assist in uncovering sources of uncertainty in the estimation approach. Therefore, the analyst is encouraged to explore the sensitivity of results using this type of analysis.

Different approaches can be taken when conducting a sensitivity analysis. Using data from different sources is one approach to assess the sensitivity of results. Mean and standard deviation from the various data sources can be derived as an indicator of the sensitivity of the outcomes. An example for undertaking a sensitivity analysis is provided below (it uses data from Case 1 and Case 2 from the asset value example above).

Undertaking a sensitivity analysis: combined value of cattle and cattle meat in Australia (2015)

Data for conducting a sensitivity analysis of cattle in Australia in 2015:

Data	Source
Asset value (1) = USD 17,112,704,685	Case 1 (see above)
Asset value (2) = USD 12,344,016,262	Case 2 (see above)

Calculation of mean value of the two asset values: $(\text{USD } 17,112,704,685 + \text{USD } 12,344,016,262) / 2 = \text{USD } 14,728,360,474$

Calculation of the standard deviation from mean asset value (see step above): USD 3,371,971,921 (use Excel, R or other software for the calculation)

The result for the standard deviation indicates that there is a relatively large spread (USD 3.3 billion) from the mean value that was derived from the two calculated asset values. This indicates a relatively high level of uncertainty in the results. In such case, the analyst could attempt to use other data sources to estimate the asset value and then re-assess the sensitivity of results.

Smith *et al.* (2024) undertook a more advanced sensitivity analysis by estimating the probability distribution of output values derived from simultaneous variations of key input parameters following a triangular distribution. A similar approach to assessing the sensitivity of results was chosen in work by LiMayberryJemberuSchrobackHerreroChatersKnight Jones *et al.* (2023). The user of this guide may refer to these publications for further information.

For analyses at national or regional/farm scale, and in cases where there are concerns about the quality of secondary data, a sensitivity analysis may also include the use of primary data, e.g. expert consultations on average biomass conversion factors, as such data sources may help to validate or improve the robustness of the results.

3.2.7 Limitations of the methodologies

It is important to note that the method used to calculate the combined asset and output value includes the risk of double counting the future output value as part of a farmed animal's current asset value (Figure 3.2) (see details in Schroback *et al.*, 2023). Another way in which asset and output values could be double counted would be if an animal were counted twice within a given year: once as a live animal (asset) and once as an animal slaughtered for meat (output).

Furthermore, a standing population in one country may also be affected by migrant herders, who move their livestock periodically across borders. Hence, it is important for analysts to verify how these dynamics are captured in national/regional data livestock population records to avoid an over- or under-estimation of the asset values for a county, or a double counting of assets in a cross-national analysis.

In the context of a global market value assessment, it is currently not possible to prevent the double counting between asset value (future output component) and output value, as information about population structures (e.g. age distribution, slaughter age), input/investment costs, salvage values and depreciation rates, is not available. However, at national level, livestock records may hold such data, which could help eliminate the double counting risk in country-level analyses. While such refined analysis to eliminate the double counting risk of asset and output value has not been done yet as part of the GBADs programme, the users of this guide should consider this in their analysis and interpretation of results.

The risk of double counting different direct-use value types is not only a concern when calculating the combined value of asset value and primary/secondary output value; it can also be an issue when calculating the combined value of asset value and the economic value of transport and draft power (Asteraye et al., 2024). As mentioned in Section 3.1.2, the addibility of these value types requires further theoretical assessment.

Furthermore, the current methodologies to estimate the economic value of farmed animals omit considerations about the externalities that farmed animal production generates, such as greenhouse gas emissions, loss of biodiversity and soil quality, and water pollution. The further development of the current methodologies needs to include ways of measuring these externalities in economic terms (e.g. using markets/prices where existing) and incorporating them into the estimation of the economic value of farmed animals, e.g. estimation of a net value.

3.2.8 Further resources

An R code which was used by Schrobback *et al.* (2023) to estimate the global economic value of farmed animals is made available for the users of this technical guide via the GBADs GitHub repository². It provides practical advice on how to calculate the asset value, output value and combined asset and output value using the R software. This code can be adapted by the user to their individual analysis context.

² <https://github.com/GBADsInformatics/TEVProject>

3.3 Interpretation of estimates and usability

When interpreting the results of the estimation, the analyst must consider the goals of the assessment and the needs it was intended to meet.

Illustrating the results often helps with their interpretation. Graphical representations of the estimates produced using the methodologies in this guide can offer insights into patterns and trends in the economic value of farmed animals for human society. Displaying the results in a graph or chart can, for example, facilitate comparisons of asset value and output value over time, or show variations by animal type (see Schrobback *et al.*, 2023). The results may also be presented in maps that illustrate the spatial distribution of the different value types for different livestock/aquaculture categories.

For example, Figure 4 provides a screenshot of the GBADs Economic Value Dashboard³, which was developed based on the methodologies and results presented by Schrobback *et al.* (2023). Illustrated is the asset value (live animals) for different livestock categories, e.g. cattle, chickens, pigs and sheep in Australia over time (1994-2018) [scale: national, focus: asset value, comparison of livestock categories, timeframe: multiple years, data: FAOSTAT]. The results show that, over the entire assessment period, the asset value of cattle was the highest, i.e. USD 15 billion and more, followed by sheep, i.e. USD 2-5 billion. This indicates that the cattle and sheep sectors contribute the highest asset value to Australian society, which is likely determined by the quantity of cattle and sheep produced and by the market prices of these livestock groups in Australia (data not shown in Figure 4). The user of the guide is encouraged to use the GBADs Economic Value Dashboard as an analysis tool and for inspiration as to how to illustrate the results of their own analysis.

The results from the economic value assessment can be the basis for investigating reasons for observed changes in economic value across time, countries, or regions. For example, in the case of the results shown in Figure 3.3, the analyst could investigate reasons for the gradual decline in the asset value of sheep and the causes for the increase and the dip (2016) in the cattle asset value for Australia. The estimated economic values for farmed animals can also be compared to the economic value generated by other food producing sectors, such as the crop sector. The information derived from such analysis can be used as a benchmark for decisions about future investments in animal health or the insurance value of farmed animals. Therefore, the analyst needs to be creative and critical in identifying ways to use the derived results for asset values, output values and combined asset and output values in a manner that best meets the specific needs and goals of the analysis.

³ [GBADs Economic Value of Livestock Dashboard \(gbadske.org\)](https://gbadske.org)

Figure 3.3 An example page from the GBADs Economic Value of Livestock Dashboard, showing the economic value of cattle, chickens, pigs, and sheep in Australia 2014-2016 in USD

Source: [GBADs Economic Value of Livestock Dashboard \(gbadske.org\)](https://gbadske.org/)

3.4 Conclusion

The purpose of this technical guide was to a) describe the economic value framework within which farmed animals can be valued, and b) describe data requirements and methodologies to calculate the economic value of farmed animals.

The methodologies presented in this guide follow a market-based approach, since the currently available methodologies and data only focus on the economic value of farmed animals that are traded in markets (Figure 3.1). Methodologies for option values and non-market values are limited in number, so only some parts of the TEV of farmed animals can currently be estimated. The analyst should be aware that the estimates derived from the use of the methodologies presented in this guide likely underestimate the TEV that farmed animals offer society (Figure 3.1). Furthermore, there are limitations to the methodologies presented in this guide, such as the potential for double counting parts of the asset and output values.

The GBADs programme intends to develop other methodologies to estimate other components of the TEV with the aim of being able to estimate the TEV in its entirety. The current technical guide will be updated as methodologies evolve. The refinement of existing and development of new methodologies will also require collaborations with inter-governmental organisations such as FAO, national governments, and livestock and aquaculture industry organisations to improve the type and quality of data collected at multiple scales.

The user of the present technical guide is also encouraged to consult the peer-reviewed literature and grey literature about advancements in the development of the methodology and about economic value estimations for farmed animals that may be being developed outside the GBADs programme.

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3.6 Economic Value: Appendix A- Inflation adjustment of price data

Inflation is the change in the price of goods (including farmed animals and the products they generate) and services in an economy over time. Inflation is measured by the price index, which is typically published by a country's national bureau of statistics or its national reserve bank. To adjust price data for inflation, analysts must choose a base year from which to start tracking price changes and they must have an understanding of the concepts of nominal value and real value.

The nominal value of prices are the actual prices that exist at a specific point in time. The real value refers to the same prices after they have been adjusted for inflation.

To convert nominal price data from several years/quarters into real data, i.e. inflation-adjusted, a starting point is selected, e.g. a base year/quarter (depending on the analysis timeframe). The nominal price value is then divided by the price index.

Step 1: Understand the link between nominal prices and real prices

$$\text{Real price} = \frac{\text{Nominal price}}{\text{Price index}/100} \quad 3.5$$

Step 2: Conduct conversion (base year 2022)

Year	Nominal price*	Price index	Calculation	Real price
2019	9079.80	79.00	9079.80 / (79/100)	11493.42
2020	9664.00	82.00	9664.00 / (82/100)	11785.37
2021	11289.70	89.00	11289.70 / (89/100)	12685.06
2022	13095.40	100.00	13095.40 / (100/100)	13095.40
2023	14958.30	110.00	14958.30 / (110/100)	13598.45

Notes: The use of a single currency should be considered for comparisons across several countries that have different currencies.

3.7 Economic Value: Appendix B- Purchasing power parity (PPP) adjustment of price data

The adjustment of prices for economic value analysis based on price data is needed due to large differences in the price levels across economies that do not use the same currency. Purchasing power parities (PPPs) are measures that are used to convert the total amount of goods and services that a single unit of a country's currency can buy in another country. The World Bank (2021) defines PPPs as follows: "PPPs are both currency conversion factors and spatial price indexes. They convert different currencies to a common currency and, in the process of conversion, equalize their purchasing power by controlling for the differences in price levels between economies. They show, with reference to a base economy, the relative price of a given basket of goods and services in each of the economies being compared. The common currency used for global comparisons is the United States dollar, e.g. USD = 1. PPP is presented as PPP\$."

Importantly, the PPP is not an exchange rate. The exchange rate between two currencies is the current rate at which one currency can be converted into another. It is determined by supply and demand in the foreign exchange market. Exchange rates are determined by the foreign exchange market through buying and selling currencies and can fluctuate significantly due to various economic factors. The exchange rate is used for international transactions, currency conversions, and foreign exchange trading. It does not consider the price differences of individual goods or services between countries.

In contrast, the PPP concept suggests a relationship between currencies based on purchasing power. It focuses on the relative purchasing power of currencies across countries. It highlights how much of a good or service can be bought with a certain amount of money in different locations. It is used for comparing living standards between countries, analysing international trade patterns, and understanding the relative cost of goods and services across borders. A limitation of the PPP concept is that PPPs are calculated only periodically and might not reflect the most recent price changes. Furthermore, currency fluctuations can impact the accuracy of PPP over time.

There are several sources that publish global datasets for PPP conversion factors:

- https://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/icp/brief/Sources_of_PPPs
- <https://databank.worldbank.org/databases/ppp>
- <https://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx?DataSetCode=PPPGDP>

If the scope of the analyst's assessment of economic value requires comparisons between currencies the following steps should be taken:

Step 1: Understand the link between nominal prices and real prices (base currency USD = 1)

$$PPP \text{ price (AUD)} = \text{Price (USD)} * PPP \text{ rate} \quad 3.6$$

Step 2: Conduct PPP adjustment two countries (see example below, base currency USD = 1)

You are interested in comparing the price of cattle between the United States (USD) and Australia (AUD) in 2011. Assume the price per head of cattle in the United States is USD 1,500. You can use the PPP for 2011 which was USD 1 = AUD 1.50¹.

To calculate the PPP for the cattle price in AUD we use the following equation:

$$PPP \text{ price (AUD)} = Price (USD) * PPP \text{ rate} \quad 3.7$$

$$PPP \text{ price (AUD)} = USD 1500 * AUD 1.50 \quad 3.8$$

$$PPP \text{ price (AUD)} = AUD 2,250 \quad 3.9$$

Based on this simplified PPP calculation, one head of cattle in Australia should theoretically cost around AUD 2,250, which is the same purchasing power as USD 1,500 in the United States. The actual price in Australia could be higher than AUD 2,250 due to factors such as production costs (feed, labour, transportation, health), cattle quality, breed, supply and demand, government policies and import/export regulation.

¹ [https://databank.worldbank.org/source/international-comparison-program-\(icp\)-2011](https://databank.worldbank.org/source/international-comparison-program-(icp)-2011)

Chapter 4 Estimating the Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE)

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Abstract

The Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE) is a new metric developed by the Global Burden of Animal Diseases (GBADs) programme aimed at quantifying the direct financial costs of diseases occurring on the farm. It calculates the difference in animal, product and input values between current farming systems and a system operating in a disease-free, ideal state without accident, injury and predation. This allows comparative analysis of the costs of animal disease facing producers in different populations.

² [GBADS – Global Burden of Animal Diseases \(animalhealthmetrics.org\)](https://animalhealthmetrics.org/)

4.1 Introduction

This chapter of the GBADs Technical Guide describes the process for estimating a “health loss envelope” for livestock, which is referred to by the GBADs programme as the Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE). The AHLE represents an envelope into which the costs of all disease should fit when attributed to cause. This is an important methodological step for ensuring the validity of disease-specific estimates, as well as providing a standalone indicator of the financial costs of disease borne by livestock producers.

This chapter focuses on the practical considerations for those wishing to perform an Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE) calculation. It includes a brief description of the conceptual background to the method, an overview of the data required for the calculation, the steps in the calculation itself, and finally guidance on how the results can be interpreted. Examples of AHLE calculation taken from GBADs case studies are presented when appropriate.

The companion paper to this guide is in preprint ahead of publication (Gilbert *et al.* 2024) and can be referred to for further detail and a discussion of the AHLE metric in greater depth. Additionally, the AHLE metric can be explored on the GBADs dashboards including its use in case studies in [Ethiopia](#) and [Senegal](#)³.

Although the guide presented in this chapter can be read as a stand-alone document, a certain level of background knowledge and familiarity with analytical techniques and applications are required to implement the methods described. Users would benefit from an understanding of animal health economics (Rushton, 2009). Familiarity with livestock population structures, production systems and livestock performance in the populations for which the user wishes to calculate the AHLE would also ease the application of the methods described. Finally, a familiarity with R Statistical Software (R Core Team, 2019) will be needed if the GBADs dynamic population model is to be applied by the user.

4.1.1 Conceptual background

Livestock agriculture uses domesticated animals to convert factors of production as inputs (land, labour and capital) into outputs (meat, milk, eggs, etc.) which can be sold or consumed by the firm or household. Optimising the productivity or efficiency of this process is a step toward improving global food security and sustainable development progress.

Livestock diseases reduce the productivity of livestock agriculture and create an economic burden which is distributed across society through increased prices for products, the use of additional resources, and increases in negative external effects, such as greenhouse gas emissions and the selection for antimicrobial resistance genes. All these effects originate at animal level, beginning with the biological effects of disease that disrupt the normal physiology of the animal, leading to reduction in productive efficiency (e.g. reduced growth, milk yield etc).

In response, animal keepers can choose to either accept a level of loss due to disease or expend additional resources mitigating disease effects. This relationship between loss and expenditure on control has been described in the literature on the economics of animal health (McInerney *et al.*, 1992).

The costs attributed to livestock disease have been described to include (Bennett, 2003):

1. Reduced quantity of products (e.g. reduced milk yield)

³ <https://gbadske.org/dashboards/ahle-casestudy/>; gbadske.org/dashboards/senegal-casestudy/

2. Reduced product quality (e.g. reduced milk quality)
3. Increased use of inputs to achieve the same level of output (e.g. increased feed use)
4. Expenditure on animal disease control inputs (e.g. cost of vaccines and antibiotics, biosecurity etc.)
5. Zoonotic disease or other human health issues (e.g. transmission of influenza viruses, bacterial enteritis, etc)
6. Reduced animal welfare (e.g. suffering due to pain)
7. Trade restriction or denial of access to market (e.g. due to Sanitary and Phytosanitary Agreement of the WTO, health-status premia on product prices)

The first four of these have been termed the “direct costs” since they are the direct physical consequences of disease on the animal, which affect production. These direct costs can be quantified by monetary units at farm level. The last three impacts (numbers 5-7) are either indirect (i.e. occur beyond the farm gate) or cannot easily be quantified in monetary units.

Rushton *et al.* (Rushton *et al.*, 2009; Rushton *et al.*, 1999) (Figure 4.1) have developed this categorisation further to present losses to disease on the farm as visible or invisible. This is an important distinction when attempting to place monetary values on changes that may not be directly valued without careful consideration of a counterfactual scenario over an extended period of time, for example changes in fertility which can result in long-term restructuring of populations.

Figure 4.1 Effects of health loss on livestock system productivity, adapted from Rushton *et al.* (1999) and Rushton (2009).

To capture both visible and invisible losses and expenditure on disease control, the GBADs programme uses farm system models which include both invisible and visible loss parameters to measure the AHLE, thereby quantifying the cost of disease at farm-level.

4.2 The Animal Health Loss Envelope approach: conceptual approach

The Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE) is a metric developed within the GBADs programme that serves multiple purposes. Firstly, the AHLE is a key part of the GBADs analytical framework, (Figure 1.1), enabling attribution of animal disease burden (Chapter 5) and assessment of the wider economic impacts of that burden (Chapter 6). Additionally, it has standalone value as a measure of the direct costs falling on producers due to animal disease.

It has been noted that in much of the scientific literature, the sum of burden estimates for individual causes of disease often results in a value greater than the total burden observed in a population (Murray & Lopez, 1999; Steenland & Armstrong, 2006). As a result, a new metric was proposed for quantifying loss and expenditure due to all causes found within the GBADs definition of disease (Torgerson & Shaw, 2021). This would serve as a validation check for single-cause estimates by placing an upper limit on the total cost of disease that could not be exceeded. With these aims in mind, the AHLE was developed by the GBADs programme (Torgerson & Shaw, 2021).

Disease burden is commonly estimated by comparison between with- and without-disease scenarios in a population of interest. The AHLE calculation is performed by modelling and comparing the productivity of livestock over an equal time period under two specific health states:

1. The **current** state of health, with current levels of disease loss and expenditure on disease control.
2. An **“ideal”** state of health in which there is no health lost to disease, and therefore also no expenditures on disease control.

Comparison of these two states allows GBADs to measure the effect of disease as a proportional loss of productive potential relative to the resources available, given a set of environmental conditions (Hennessy & Marsh, 2021). In practice this is measured as the difference in profit and livestock asset value between the current health scenario and an ideal state with no disease, over a fixed time period.

To understand the ideal health state, the question “*what does GBADs include in its measurement of disease?*” needs to be answered. A working definition of the ideal health state in livestock is:

“A normality in bodily structure and function that provides the ability to perform physiologic functions at normal levels, given nutrition and other environmental requirements are provided at adequate levels (Marcovitch, 2017; Studdert et al., 2020)”.

There are two important parts in this definition:

- That in ideal health, no physiological function in the animal is disrupted in a measurable way that can be classified as a disease.
- That for ideal health to exist, a set of environmental and feed conditions must fall within a range to be considered “adequate” in both quality and quantity so as not to directly cause disease.

Comparison of the two scenarios (current vs ideal) for an equal time period then allows the all-cause direct financial costs of disease at farm-level to be quantified through its effect on production. This fulfils the objective of placing an envelope around the potential burden of disease incurred by individual causes.

Figure 4.2 Illustration of the relationship between the AHLE, expenditure on disease control, and the enterprise profit under current, zero mortality, and ideal health scenarios.

4.3 The approach in practice

The AHLE calculation uses a farm or enterprise budgeting framework that will already be familiar to many stakeholders in livestock production systems. The enterprise budget is a tool for representing the relationship between inputs provided to the livestock production enterprise (land and feed, animals, labour etc) and outputs generated, valued by their respective prices. This framework has been described in detail in agricultural economics textbooks, for example Rushton (Rushton, 2009) provides an in-depth breakdown of farm budgeting in livestock production, and we encourage readers to explore such resources for additional background. Given the broad range of production systems to which GBADs is intended to cater, the use of a farm budgeting framework will be of benefit to stakeholders looking to apply GBADs methods, as it offers a familiar and generic approach for recording farm financial performance.

4.3.1 Population modelling

The process of accounting for the impact of health change on the efficiency of production within GBADs is based on the use of models of the farm system. A set of standard dynamic population models (DPM) have been produced and others are in development, to allow quantification of farm performance under different productivity scenarios using the R statistical software. The development and progress of these models can be followed for:

- Grazing-based systems for cattle and small ruminants [here](#)⁴
- Scavenge-based systems for pigs and chickens (in development)
- Growing or fattening animal systems (pigs, chickens, aquaculture) (in development)
- Laying hen systems (in development)
- Working equids (in development)

Please note that code development and optimisation is ongoing. The linked GitHub repositories record this development and provide example code, but are different stages of readiness for use. The dynamic population models each come with their own set of required data inputs which are outlined below (Section 4.5).

The DPM is used to calculate the productivity of a given population (e.g. pastoral cattle in Ethiopia) over a one-year time period. The model simulates the dynamic growth of that population, as well as the inputs required (e.g. feed, labour etc) and the resulting production outputs (e.g. live animals, meat, milk, dung etc). Inputs and outputs are assigned monetary values based on market prices, which enables the profit of the simulated population to be calculated. To calculate the AHLE, the DPM can be run with different sets of parameters representing the current and ideal scenarios described above.

The DPM has been used in several GBADs case studies including in Ethiopia, Senegal and Indonesia. Further details of these case studies can be found on the GBADs website ([here](#)) and knowledge engine ([here](#)). The DPM also forms the basis of the methodology described in the chapter of the GBADs technical guide on attribution (Chapter 5).

4.3.2 Scale of the approach

An AHLE calculation can be undertaken at a variety of different scales, depending on the needs of the user. To date, the GBADs Ethiopian case study has calculated an AHLE for cattle, small ruminants and poultry at national and sub-national scales⁵ When undertaking an assessment of animal disease

⁴ <https://github.com/GBADsInformatics/GBADsDPM.R>

⁵ <https://gbadske.org/dashboards/ahle-casestudy/>

burdens the geographic scale should be decided based on user needs and the population of interest, and data used should be appropriate to this population and scale.

4.3.3 Time scale

The AHLE is calculated over a period of one year. The DPM uses a monthly time step and runs for a one-year period. The selection of model time steps from which to calculate the AHLE is a compromise between improving the precision of estimates and the processing power needed to run the model. In general, the faster the flock or herd production cycle, the shorter the timestep required in the model; for example, the GBADs pig production model developed for use in Indonesia, will use a 1-week timestep.

4.3.4 Other key assumptions

To date, GBADs case studies have focused principally on production systems which have very few fixed cost inputs (housing, machinery, salaried labour etc). These have mostly been extensive and pastoral smallholder production systems. When fixed costs approximate to zero, a gross margin approximates to profit. This has been the approach used in the GBADs Ethiopian and Senegal case studies.

4.4 Methods

The AHLE is calculated by estimating the difference in animal investment, resource use, products generated, and disease control expenditure between the current and ideal health scenarios, resulting in a monetary value of disease cost. This section first shows how a structural model of a population of interest can be built to represent the relationships between these inputs and outputs. The construction of a structural model facilitates understanding of where the visible and invisible costs of disease are incurred and the identification of the parameters that need to change to quantify ideal health performance. Following that, an AHLE calculation is described in general terms. The use of the GBADs DPM is covered in more detail, with the small ruminant model for Ethiopia as an example (Section 4.4.4). A full account of this work can be read here (Jemberu *et al.*, 2023).

4.4.1 Structural model of population under current health

A method for describing a livestock population in a manner suitable for calculating an AHLE is described below. A hypothetical production system is described to illustrate the step-by-step process of building a structural model of a population.

4.4.1.1 Products and exits from the livestock system

One way to approach the construction of a livestock system model is to begin with the products that it generates, their quantities, any quality distinctions, and respective prices. This must include all exits of animals or products, irrespective of whether they carry any value. For example, unhatched eggs, aborted pregnancies, condemned carcasses etc.

Consider a simple livestock production system which produces live animals for sale, slaughters animals for meat, and from which live animals are lost at a given mortality rate (Figure 4.3). Each exit route requires a quantity or number of output units (e.g. number of animals) over time, and a price per unit (in the case of mortality the price may well be zero). Any additional product information which may be needed to stratify quantities and prices on exit routes can also be gathered at this point, such as animal age, sex or weight for sales, carcass gradings for slaughter, etc.

Figure 4.3 Animal and product exits from a simple livestock production system.

4.4.1.2 Population compartmentalisation

Working back from the list of exit routes from the population (Figure 4.3), each must be traced back to its source within the population, from which subsets of the population can be derived. In most cases, this will relate to age or sex differentiated compartments of the population. For example, milk and eggs are derived from adult female animals. Where birth of young is contingent on both male and female animals, the adult female compartment most often sets the limit on birth rate and can therefore be assumed as the source for animal births. The rate at which each product leaves each compartment of the population must be determined either from data or by calculation.

In our simplified example, excess young animals are sold when they reach a certain age if they are not transferred into the standing adult population. Adult animals are sold for slaughter at a given age (Figure 4.4). As a result, live and slaughter exits are not stratified in any way. In this example, mortality occurring at different ages is associated with different unit costs, so the mortality exit is stratified into age groups.

Figure 4.4 Source compartments within the population leading to each exit route for animals or products, differentiated by age (Adult, Juvenile).

The second step is to describe any interdependencies between compartments where animals exit one compartment and enter another during the analysis period, since the rate of these movements is often influenced by health (Figure 4.4). Animal movements into compartments from external sources, such as imports and purchases should also be identified.

Figure 4.5 Population compartments with interdependencies. Adult and Juvenile compartments are connected by reproductive and growth rates.

4.4.1.3 Inputs to compartments

Fixed and variable inputs to each compartment must be listed. These must be divided into ordinary inputs (those which are always needed, irrespective of health state) and disease control inputs (those which are used specifically as prophylaxis or in response to disease). A usage rate with respect to an appropriate unit of measurement related to the scale of production is also needed for each input (Figure 4.6). This rate describes the allocation of inputs per unit of population within the compartment, for example, feed mass per animal per year.

Figure 4.6 Inputs provided to the animal population, connected to the livestock population compartments by usage rates.

This completes the construction of the structural system model. Following this, the model should be used to populate a list of the total quantities, prices and values of all animals, products, disease control and ordinary inputs in and out of the system over the course of a year, including change in standing population value between year start and year end. The resulting value is the profit of the system under investigation under current conditions. For grazing systems, this can be calculated using the DPM which simulates a more developed structural system model than the one described here (see Section 4.4.4).

4.4.2 Adjustment for ideal health

The next step is to perform the same calculation under the ideal health conditions. While any individual animal in the population may achieve an ideal health state at a given moment according to the definition laid out in section 4.2, GBADs measures the AHLE over a standard time of one year. The setting of ideal health parameters may very well necessitate extrapolating performance beyond that observed in the field, even in the best performing farms and animals. The ideal health state is therefore a hypothetical rather than an achievable state, able to be maintained under field conditions.

This procedure for ideal health adjustment begins with identifying the rates within the model that change when the ideal health condition is imposed. Some of these rate changes are set by convention for the AHLE calculation, meaning they are based on key assumptions made to describe

the ideal health state and are assumed to be consistent across all AHLE calculations. Other rate changes may be context dependent.

The following rates are set by convention:

- All mortality is set to zero rate for all compartments of the population.
- All exit or yield rates for animals or products which are by-products of disease or morbidity are set to zero (e.g. carcase condemnation).
- All input usage rates which are entirely dependent on the presence of disease are set to zero (therefore zero disease-control inputs used).

And the additional constraints are imposed:

- Total output of products (in the example case, this means slaughter animals and live animal sales) should be minimised, with the condition that each cannot be less than the current health scenario. This should be achieved by rate adjustment and reduction in total livestock in the standing population, inflows of live animals to the standing population, and ordinary input use.

Where necessary, population dynamic rates within the model can be adjusted to represent performance in the absence of disease. In the example case, this refers to reproduction and growth rates which determine the movement of animals between population compartments (Figure 4.5).

Yield rates for each remaining exit or product can now be adjusted to represent ideal health, from which the productive animal population necessary for the ideal health scenario can be calculated. Accordingly, each individual ordinary input use rate can also then be adjusted. This should include any fixed cost infrastructure utilisation adjusted for ideal health population size, where for example, stocking densities must be adjusted for the absence of mortality. Following this, required ordinary input quantities can be calculated for the ideal health population size.

4.4.3 Calculation of AHLE

Following calculation of ordinary input values, total output values and disease control input for both current and ideal scenarios, the AHLE calculation can be performed. Compared to a standard enterprise profit or gross margin calculation there are some further factors to consider. Because the productivity of the animal changes with different health states, the AHLE must capture the value of both production and use of resources, but also any change in the capital value of live animals in the system which result from constraining system output.

For this reason, the AHLE calculation places animal exits and population growth within the total of outputs, however animals moving into the population ("animals in"), and the starting herd value at the initial time are accounted for separately and compared between the two scenarios.

The AHLE is therefore:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \textit{Total ordinary input value (current)} - \textit{Total ordinary input value (ideal)} \\
 & \quad + \textit{Total disease control input value (current)} \\
 & \quad + \textit{Total "animals in" value (current)} - \textit{Total "animals in" value (ideal)} \\
 & \quad - (\textit{Total output value (ideal)} - \textit{Total output value (current)})
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

In addition, calculation of a third, intermediate scenario is recommended: the zero-mortality scenario. This uses the ideal health scenario but reverts the population dynamics and yield rates to

current health performance levels, while maintaining the zero-mortality condition. This isolates the cost of mortality, which can then be subtracted from the full AHLE to compare the relative contribution of mortality and production loss to the total AHLE.

It is recommended that uncertainty in parameters should be accounted for and described through an appropriate process of sensitivity analysis following this calculation.

4.4.4 Calculating the AHLE using the GBADs Dynamic Population Model

The GBADs DPM has been used in Ethiopia to calculate the AHLE (Jemberu *et al.*, 2023). An overview of this process is set out below as a worked example.

Any model used to represent a study population should be as close to reality as the data and computational power, time and resources allow. For small ruminants in Ethiopia a schematic of the population structural model, on which the DPM v1 is based, can be seen in Figure 4.7. In this system, population level data for small ruminants were available from the national statistical agency census data (CSA census data is accessible through the [GBADs Knowledge Engine](#)), and these data separate small ruminants into 6 age-sex groups: males and females age <6 months, 6-12 months and >12 months. Thus, based on the data available and prior knowledge of the production systems to be investigated, including knowledge of the management of these animals and the diseases they incur, the 6 age-sex groups were used to represent the population.

The following population structure is described:

- Animals move from the <6-months group into the 6–12-months group, and from there into the >12 months group at fixed maturation rates. The maturation rates are fixed based on the proportion of the population in each age-sex strata at t0 and the duration of stay in each stratum (6 months) (Rates derived from CSA census database).
- New animals are added to the <6-months male and female strata through applying a reproduction rate * litter size calculation to all adult females at each time step, calculating a number born, and splitting this evenly between the <6-months male and female groups.
- Animals are removed from each age-sex stratum through applying an age-sex specific mortality rate to each group at each time step (mortality rates are derived from CSA census database).
- Adult males and females are also removed through application of an age-sex specific cull rate at the end of their reproductive lives (cull rate derived from CSA census database).
- Live animal offtake represents animals killed for meat; an age-sex specific offtake rate is applied to each age-sex stratum (offtake rate derived from CSA census database).
- Manure is produced from all age-sex groups. Expected daily manure production is calculated for all animals in each age-sex strata for each time step (1 month). Manure volume (kg) is multiplied by average market value for the year being modelled to give a total system income from manure.
- Hides are salvaged from 50% of the dead animals in the Ethiopian system model.
- System inputs required for each age-sex group were feed, labour, and health care costs:
 - Health care costs was compiled of preventative health care costs such as vaccination, and treatment costs such as veterinary time and antibiotics.

For all model parameters, distributions are used to draw parameter values stochastically, and the model is run for 10,000 iterations to produce expected value distributions. Where literature data are used to inform parameter values systematic literature searches were carried out, followed by meta-analysis to combine values for informing the parameter distribution. A one-month time step was

used to run the model to remove the competing risks problem for the different demographic events (offtakes and mortalities etc) and to allow incorporation of dynamic pathogen models in future versions of the population model for disease specific attribution.

After 1 year the enterprise budget for the represented population was calculated by summing the value of; flock change plus outputs (offtake, manure, hides) minus expenditure on food, labour, healthcare. The model was parameterised for the current scenario using literature and census data (through formalised meta-analysis process) and for the ideal scenario using expert elicitation (Cooke's classical method) to elicit parameter values with subject experts in Ethiopia. The difference between the enterprise budget for the ideal and current scenario is the animal health loss envelope for this production system, in the modelled year.

Figure 4.7. Schematic of the population structural model for the small ruminant dynamic population model as applied by GBADs to the small ruminant populations of Ethiopia.

4.5 Data requirements

The data requirements for calculating an animal health loss envelope fall into two categories by subject:

- The data necessary for valuing the livestock enterprise.
- The data required to adjust for performance under ideal health.

A full list of the parameters and data requirements for GBADs DPM can be found in the GBADs data dictionary. This is not currently available publicly but is available on request.

4.5.1 The livestock enterprise

Detailed instructions on the construction of farm enterprise budgets can be found in published textbooks (Rushton, 2009). Briefly, for a standard enterprise budget, the quantities and prices of the inputs and outputs of the livestock enterprise are required (see Table 4.1). Each item requires quantity and price data (Rushton, 2009). Specifics may vary according to the population under study. For example, the extensive and pastoral grazing systems of Ethiopia approximate to having zero fixed-cost inputs, so this column is ignored.

Table 4.1. Items required to construct a typical farm enterprise budget.

Fixed inputs	Variable inputs	Outputs
Salaried labour	Animal feed	Animals and products sold.
Machinery	Health care inputs	Animals and products consumed at home.
Animal housing	Casual labour	Animals and products bought.
Maintenance costs	Other items	Livestock and products gifted or received.
Rent		Change in herd value over the reporting period.
Heating, electricity, water		

In addition, when used for an AHLE calculation the description of the livestock enterprise requires data on animal and product losses due to disease, even where they may not be recorded in a traditional enterprise budget because they incur no direct monetary cost. Depending on markets, this could include losses such as stillborn animals, abortions, disease culls, carcasses condemned at slaughter as unsafe for consumption, etc. From the enterprise budget under current health, calculations of resource use, growth rates and valuations etc. are facilitated by data on liveweight values of the animals that make up the population in the different age-sex strata. For further information on liveweight biomass and estimation of animal value, please see Chapter 2 and Chapter 3 on estimation of biomass and economic value respectively.

Data used to parameterise the desired budget format would ideally report quantity and price for each input and output over a standard time period of one year. However, data formats do not always report these values directly, so some calculation is often needed to determine quantities and prices. For example, depending on the population being assessed, data may be found to use different denominators to express productivity such as rates of growth, resource use and product yield (Table 4.2). Fixed assets costs are often expressed as a cost per metre squared of housing, whereas feed and other variable inputs can be reported as a quantity per animal head per year or per cycle, as per unit of housing area, as a cost per unit of output generated, or simply as a quantity per unit time (e.g. tonnes per year). Additionally, certain ways of reporting resource-use through productivity may

be preferred in specific systems. For example, in growing animal systems feed use is often described by productivity rather than quantity through a feed conversion ratio, which is the change in animal liveweight divided by the total feed mass supplied. Being a ratio, this is a dimensionless number, but if the quantity of either numerator or denominator is known, the other quantity can be calculated. For example, when total production of meat is known by mass for a one-year period, feed use can be calculated from the feed conversion ratio.

Data need to be sufficient to allow all inputs and outputs used or generated to be related through quantifying a rate over a common denominator. Very often, the animal (head or liveweight) provides the means to do this.

Data availability and quality varies substantially between and within countries, species and production systems. Given this variability the sources of data, data flows, processing and calculations performed to produce the required format of data to estimate an AHLE should be thoroughly documented as part of the reporting process.

Table 4.2. Commonly used denominators to express productivity in livestock production systems.

Rate	Commonly used denominators
Input consumption (or output generation)	Per animal per unit time
	Per metre squared of housing per unit time
	Per unit of product out (or input used)
	Per unit time
	Per kilogram liveweight per unit time
	Per physiological cycle (e.g. lactation, gestation, etc.)

4.5.2 Data needs for productivity change under ideal health conditions

4.5.2.1 Setting adequate nutrition and ordinary inputs, and normal environmental conditions

Setting the environmental, nutritional, and input provision levels suitable for the ideal state requires knowledge of the normal environmental conditions and resource availability of the study population. Data required for this step therefore include data on these factors over time, such as climate and meteorological data. In addition to the physical environment, information on the market and legislative environments of producers should be collected to understand how production outcomes might change or be constrained in ideal health. As GBADs becomes established over time, the building of datasets that allow ideal health parameter estimation to account for geographical and temporal variation in environmental conditions is expected to become possible. Refinement of the conditions and assumptions around the ideal health state in different populations and systems are ongoing within the GBADs programme, as are adaptations to reflect these in the DPM. For example, consideration of limits on grazing land availability will be imposed in ideal health scenarios in future iterations.

At present however, ideal health parameters are based on biologically plausible maximums, legislative limits, or careful adjustment of individual parameters through expert consultation. For example, where quotas on production are imposed, or restrictions on animal stocking densities maintained, a hard limit can be placed on the appropriate parameter within a model to reflect the legislative limits. To date, GBADs case studies have combined published literature and census data, and a consultative process with country or context experts to set the ideal conditions. An overview of the data requirements is presented in Table 4.3. This table also indicates possible data sources for key parameters.

Table 4.3. Data requirements for the dynamic population model

Variable category	Variable	Stratification	Definition	Possible data sources	
				Current scenario	Ideal scenario
Population	Population	Stratified by age and sex	Number of animals in population at time 0	FAO, GBADs Knowledge engine etc, Government statistics agencies	Can be calculated from other input variables
Growth	Liveweight	Stratified by age and sex	Average liveweight of an animal	Slaughter data, scientific publications, IPCC statistics, FAO, genetics companies, private sector companies.	Genetics companies, mechanistic modelling output, expert elicitation
Reproduction	Parturition rate	Adult females	Average number of litters per adult female per year	Farm data, livestock identification and movement data	Genetics companies, mechanistic modelling output, expert elicitation, biological limitations.
	Litter size	Adult females	Average number offspring born per litter	Farm data, livestock identification and movement data	Genetics companies, mechanistic modelling output, expert elicitation, biological limitations.
Mortality	Mortality	Stratified by age and sex	Mortality due to direct loss from animal health issues including disease/injury etc as a proportion of the population in each time period	Farm data, census data, livestock identification and movement data, household survey data	Always zero
Outputs	Live animals (offtake)	Stratified by age and sex	Animals removed from the herd, which includes animals sold or slaughtered for meat (i.e.	Slaughter statistics, export statistics, livestock identification	No output quantity reduced compared to current scenario.

			removed from herd with financial value), as well as those removed from the herd as gifts	and movement data, FAO statistics	
Carcase yield	Stratified by age and sex	Average proportion of liveweight retained following dressing of carcase		Slaughter statistics, meat producer associations, private sector companies, FAO statistics	Slaughter statistics and carcase conformation data, expert elicitation
Proportion milked	Adult females	Proportion of adult females that are milked after they give birth		Farm data, scientific publications, household surveys, private sector companies, FAO statistics	
Days milked	Adult females	Average number of days lactating animals are milked for		Scientific publications, farm data, research station reports, private sector companies	Biological limits and calving interval calculation
Milk yield	Adult females	Average yield for an animal through her lactation		Scientific publications, farm data, private sector data, research station reports, FAO statistics	Genetics companies, breeder associations, farm data, research station data, scientific publications, mechanistic modelling
Others such as wool, cashmere, draught power etc dependant on the system	As appropriate	Average output per animal per model time period		Scientific publications, farm data, research station reports, private sector data	Genetics companies, breeder associations, farm data, research station data, scientific publications, mechanistic modelling

Inputs	Live animals purchased	Stratified by age and sex	Number of animals entering the study population from external sources	FAO statistics, Trade statistics, farm data, household surveys, private sector companies.	Calculation
	Fixed costs		Infrastructure costs per head	Farm budget reports, producer association reports, private sector companies.	Calculation
	Feed		Feed costs per month	Feed manufacturer associations, Government statistics, FAO statistics, market reports.	Calculation, expert elicitation, mechanistic modelling techniques
	Health care		Costs of animal health care per month	Government statistics, FAO statistics, market reports, private sector companies.	Always zero
	Labour		Cost of labour per month	Feed manufacturer associations, Government statistics, FAO statistics, market reports, World Bank statistics	Calculation, expert elicitation
Prices	Prices of outputs and inputs		Average market value per unit (see also EV guide)	FAO data, Government reports, private sector data.	Constant pricing assumed between scenarios

4.5.3 Data sources for ideal health estimation

Production parameters under ideal health are largely hypothetical in nature as production in the complete absence of disease is not achievable under real-world conditions for a whole population over an entire year.

Data sources for ideal health parameters therefore present a challenge. Some of the possible sources of data are described below.

Biological limits and mechanistic models: Some parameters, such as parturition rate and litter size, have clear biological limits depending on species, for example a cow has a gestation length of 9 months and is usually anoestrus after giving birth for at least 45 days, thus it would be biologically impossible to reproduce successfully more than every 10.5 months. In practice, most producers allow some post-partum recovery time so an expected average reproduction rate of once a year becomes a plausible target. For other parameters (e.g. milk yield or growth rate) there is likely to be a biological maximum from an animal based on its capacity for metabolizable energy intake and genetics, balanced with its health and welfare.

It is important to consider the production system and environmental conditions when choosing data to represent the ideal health state. Ideal values should be appropriate to the population under study. For example, if the AHLE is being calculated for pastoral cattle in Ethiopia it would not be appropriate to use the maximum milk yield for a high-producing Holstein Friesian on a US dairy farm to parameterise the ideal health scenario.

Expert elicitation: In GBADs case studies in Ethiopia, Senegal and Indonesia, structured expert elicitation was used to determine parameter values under ideal health conditions. Expert elicitation approaches have several drawbacks, including high uncertainty around expert judgements and the considerable financial and time costs of undertaking workshops. However, where data is lacking, structured expert elicitation may provide formal, transparent methods to capture, analyse and synthesise the knowledge and opinions of experts.

It is beyond the scope of this guide to describe the methodology and results of GBADs case studies. Briefly, expert elicitation workshops were conducted using Cooke's (Classical) method of structured expert elicitation, a well-established and verified methodology which has been used extensively in other domains when data is lacking (Hoffmann *et al.*, 2017). Experts with specific knowledge of local livestock production, were invited to estimate probability distributions (5th, 50th and 95th centiles) of parameters under the ideal health scenario and the results used to parameterise the ideal scenario in the AHLE calculation.

Validation of ideal health parameter estimates: Pairs of parameters for the current and ideal scenario should be examined for consistency. When extracted from different data sources (e.g. literature versus expert opinion), parameters may have been measured and defined in different ways while a consistent parameter definition is needed for all data sources. Additionally, different data sources may have been collected in different locations and times within the same study population. Difference in measurement technique (e.g. sample size, sampling method) can produce apparently inconsistent results due to uncertainty around parameter estimates.

With these sources of difference in mind, pairwise comparison for each parameter in the two scenarios should consider these factors and attempt to resolve any anomalous results (e.g. yield rates lower per animal in the ideal health scenario compared to the current scenario). As with all steps in the AHLE calculation, this should be fully documented as part of the process.

4.5.4 Consideration of uncertainty

Uncertainty around estimates is inevitable but a hierarchy of evidence approach should be used, following a systematic process (Evans, 2003), to ensure the best data available is used to parameterise models, and all steps of the process, and potential sources of uncertainty, should be documented. Large datasets with representative measures of the required parameters, specific to the target population, would be the preferred resource for calculating the AHLE. However, such datasets are rarely available. Data derived from systematic searching and meta-analysis of literature may be used as an alternative, followed by secondary data sources. Imputed data and data from expert elicitation may be necessary if other data sources, higher up the hierarchy are unavailable.

Wherever possible distributions should be used to describe parameters, based on primary data or on summary statistics (e.g. mean, median) with measures of spread (e.g. maximum and minimum, standard deviation, quartiles), to allow variability to be quantified in the results of the analysis. If this is not possible, deterministic calculations can be performed using point estimates for specific values. In the DPM parameters can be entered as distributions (e.g. using minimum, maximum and modal values) or as point estimates depending on data availability¹.

¹ <https://github.com/GBADsInformatics/GBADsDPM.R>

4.6 Interpretation of results

The AHLE represents a total financial cost borne by producers due to disease. The utility of this metric is divided into two categories, its internal utility as a step toward other metrics of disease burden, and its value as a standalone metric that can be communicated to relevant stakeholders.

4.6.1 The AHLE as a methodological step

- The AHLE sets the top boundary for productivity change within the population being assessed. This boundary cannot be exceeded by individual or combined estimates for disease cost due to individual causes (see Chapter 5).
- The models used at farm and economy level to calculate the AHLE (section 0) also allow characterisation of incremental change between current and ideal scenarios, for example due to the presence or absence of specific diseases. The resulting disease attribution process is described in Chapter 5. **Error! Reference source not found.**
- The AHLE is used as an input to partial and general equilibrium models which incorporate supply-demand relationships to look at price and quantity change in a dynamic manner in response to the farm-level productivity change described in the AHLE calculation process. This estimates economic burden and identifies the winners and losers across society when health status changes. These methods are described in detail in Chapter 6.
- In future, the AHLE calculation may be disaggregated by stratifying the producer population to look at gender and other possible distributional effects. Connection of the AHLE result to other models will allow the total impact of animal disease on externalities such as greenhouse gas emissions and the spread of antimicrobial resistance genes to be quantified.

4.6.2 The AHLE as a standalone metric

The external utility of the AHLE to stakeholders is expected to be at national or international policy decision making levels rather than at farm level.

- The AHLE approximates the farm-level costs of disease, assuming prices are fixed. As a result, it is not a complete measure of disease burden in society. This is because it does not incorporate changes in price of inputs to or outputs of production (for example, feed demand & supply, labor demand & supply, vaccine demand & supply, meat and milk demand & supply, etc) and are unfettered by regulatory/policy constraints (e.g, trade restrictions). These aspects can be taken into consideration elsewhere (Chapter 6)
- The AHLE measures disease cost at farm-level but is not a farm-level decision-making tool, since it is based on a hypothetical ideal rather than a target to be aimed at. It complements other metrics such as farm benchmarking which are geared toward producer decision making.
- When compared to farm benchmarking, the gap between the best producers and the AHLE illustrates the potential area for new technologies to be made available to address health and disease issues which are currently not being dealt with effectively.
- The AHLE allows comparative analysis between different populations by standardising what is measured at farm-level and over what time period. For example, the relative size of gaps between average, best current-scenario benchmarks, and ideal health may be informative when compared across different populations and help to identify producer populations under the highest level of disease pressure or with the least access to control inputs.
- Costs of morbidity and mortality can be compared between different species and enterprise types, in different locations, and over time. The AHLE can be broken down into mortality and lost production, as well as relative expenditure on disease control interventions. These can

then be compared to identify policy and market interventions, such as those setting access to disease control, and can be used as an aid to building a business case for such interventions. An example of the breakdown of the AHLE into mortality, expenditure, and production loss, from the GBADs Senegal case study, can be found in Figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8. Division of the AHLE between production losses, mortality (animal) losses, and animal health expenditure for small ruminant production in Senegal

Detailed examples of the result of the AHLE calculations can be found on the GBADs Dashboards for [Ethiopia](#) and [Senegal](#), and we encourage users to explore these examples when reading this guide or undertaking their own AHLE assessments.

4.7 Summary

- The Animal Health Loss Envelope (AHLE) is a new metric developed by GBADs to quantify the cost of disease at farm level across a population.
- The cost of disease is made up of increased spending on inputs (expenditure) and reduced yield of outputs (losses).
- The AHLE measures the total cost of disease due to all causes simultaneously. This creates an “envelope” into which individual causes must fit, thereby preventing overestimation of burden.
- The AHLE also captures the costs of diseases which are not being managed or controlled across the population, with the potential to identify populations where interventions may be needed to widen access to disease control technologies.
- Disease reduces farm productivity, resulting in additional resources being used to produce an equal volume of output when compared to a disease-free ideal. The AHLE represents the value of this change in productivity.
- Valuing productivity change means valuing the resources consumed, and products generated by an animal, as well as any change in the value of the animal itself over a standard time period. The AHLE calculation uses a one-year period as standard.
- Animal outputs include growth and reproduction of animal biomass, sales of animals, yield of meat, milk and eggs, materials such as hides and wool, waste products like manure and slurry, and draught and transport power.
- Inputs to production include animals bought in to the population from external sources and the ordinary inputs needed by animals to fulfil their economic purpose such as land and feed, labour, capital inputs such as housing and machinery, and other basic necessities such as water, and the energy used to heat and ventilate housing.
- Veterinary and biosecurity spending is identified as a special class of input: disease control expenditure, which is provided to mitigate losses to disease.
- The AHLE is calculated as the difference between total value of inputs, outputs, animals and disease control expenditure between two scenarios:
 - The current scenario, with animals in their real-world health states
 - The ideal health scenario, where zero disease means reduced resource requirements to produce each unit of output, and there is no expenditure on disease control.
- Performing this calculation is facilitated by population models which estimate the dynamic changes resulting from improvements in biological parameters such as fertility and growth under ideal health.
- Population and production changes are quantified as monetary value using a farm budgeting framework.
- This metric has been applied in GBADs case studies in [Ethiopia](#) and [Senegal](#).
- These case studies have used a GBADs Dynamic Population Model (DPM) to calculate. This model is publicly available to [download](#) and runs in R Statistical software.

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Chapter 5 Attributing the burden of animal disease to specific causes

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Abstract

The purpose of this guide is to offer practical information for livestock production analysts, researchers and policy makers on how to attribute the burden of disease to specific causes in farmed animals. It describes a seven-step framework for estimating the cause-specific losses. The chapter proposes different methods to consider in the analysis, reviews data requirements and discusses challenges associated with disease attribution. The approaches can be adapted to analyses at global, national, or sub-national scales. Links to relevant references and associated documentation are provided to offer practical advice.

² [GBADS – Global Burden of Animal Diseases \(animalhealthmetrics.org\)](https://animalhealthmetrics.org/)

5.1 Introduction

5.1.1 Purpose and scope of the present chapter

The Global Burden of Animal Diseases (GBADs) programme aims to provide a consistent and comparable description of diseases and their impact on production, animal welfare and human health across animal production systems, time, and geographical location. The methodological approaches used for burden of disease studies in farmed animals – often termed economic, cost or impact studies – are not standardised, which impedes the ability to compare estimates of the burden of specific diseases across studies, within and between production systems, and between different diseases (Huntington *et al.*, 2021; Rushton *et al.*, 2021). To improve accuracy, utility and comparability, GBADs quantifies the burden of animal disease using a yield gap measure, termed the animal health loss envelope (AHLE) (Gilbert *et al.*, 2024). The theoretical concepts and practical methods for calculating the AHLE of a particular population of animals is described in Chapter 4. Briefly, the AHLE encompasses both production losses due to morbidity and mortality, and expenditure on animal health. This AHLE can be calculated as the difference between the gross margin for the theoretical ideal health scenario with no morbidity or mortality due to disease and zero health expenditure, and the gross margin for the current health scenario that includes production losses due to disease and health expenditure.

While the all-cause AHLE encompasses the costs incurred by all animal health issues combined, decision-making may also require more detailed knowledge of the burden specifically due to individual causes, or groups of causes. This process is termed ‘attribution’ and is the focus of the present chapter. The attribution of the disease burden by specific causes, or groups of causes, can be performed both in absolute terms (total costs), and in relative terms (proportion of the all-cause burden attributable to the cause(s) of interest). The purpose of this chapter is to provide an overarching framework for attributing the AHLE to specific causes, or groups of causes, and offer practical guidance on conducting the analyses, including accounting for comorbidities. The chapter starts with introducing the conceptual framework to attribution currently used by GBADs (Section 5.2), followed by detailed explanations of the methods (Section 0). Section 5.4 outlines data requirements and possible sources of data, while Section 5.5 provides suggestions on the interpretation of results.

The complexity of disease causation is a significant challenge when calculating the cause-specific burden of disease. For this reason, GBADs has been exploring several approaches, identifying advantages and limitations of the different options. The approaches presented in this chapter thus represent work in progress and are not intended to provide definitive guidance. As methods are further developed, adopted and implemented across the GBADs programme, this progress will be recorded in updated versions of the Technical Guide.

5.1.2 Skills required to implement the method

Each GBADs chapter requires different levels of prior knowledge and skills to be able to effectively implement the methods. Given the computationally heavy nature of the method described below those wishing to use this method should have a familiarity with R statistical environment and an understanding of the key tenets of frequentist and Bayesian approaches to data analysis. If the user does not have the required skillset, we suggest they familiarise themselves with these techniques prior to undertaking an attribution study. However, we anticipate that this chapter will still provide users without prior knowledge in these areas with an understanding of the method and the interpretation of the results.

5.2 Overview of the approach to disease burden attribution

5.2.1 Classification of causes of disease

Attributing the burden of disease by causes requires a working definition of what is encompassed by the term ‘disease’. For GBADs, disease is defined as “an abnormal condition that adversely affects the structure or function leading to an inability to perform physiologic functions at normal levels” (Bruce *et al.*, 2024; Gilbert *et al.*, 2024). The outcome of a disease is reflected in decreased efficiency of converting inputs (such as feed and water) into outputs (such as milk and meat). Diseases can be defined either by their cause (aetiology³) or by the sequelae they are associated with (disease syndrome). Disease syndromes such as abortion, lameness, or mastitis may have more than one aetiology. Reciprocally, a given aetiology may produce different syndromes; for example, brucellosis may be associated with lameness, abortion, or other sequelae. Examples of diseases by aetiology include:

- Foot and mouth disease (FMD) as the clinical manifestation of infection with the virus *Aphthovirus vesiculae* (formerly known and commonly referred to as foot-and-mouth disease virus, FMDv)
- Peste des petits ruminants (PPR) as the clinical manifestation of infection with the virus *Morbillivirus caprinae* (formerly known and commonly referred to as peste-des-petits-ruminants virus (PPRV) or small ruminant morbillivirus)

The attribution process is concerned with *causes* of disease, which are classified for this purpose using a hierarchy of four levels (Figure 5.1):

- Level 1 causes (hereafter referred to as high-level causes) are broad categories of causes encompassing all causes of ill health in animals: infectious, non-infectious, and external causes (Larkins *et al.*, 2023)
- Level 2 aggregates specific causes by body system (e.g., musculoskeletal causes) or aetiological group (e.g., nutritional disorders)
- Level 3 includes specific aetiological causes of disease such as *Brucella* spp., PPRv, FMDv, pregnancy hypocalcaemia, and predation. For most causes, Level 3 causes are the most detailed classification available, but an additional level of detail may be available for some specific causes
- Level 4 differentiates level 3 causes by key characteristics such as strain or serotype. For example, FMDv has seven immunologically distinct serotypes: A, O, C, SAT1, SAT2, SAT3, and Asia1. Given that the serotypes do not confer cross immunity, disease caused by a particular serotype can be thought of as a specific variation of FMD, and so has its own level 4 grouping

This cause classification is mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive at every level of aggregation. It provides a grouping method that separates causes into subsets and does not double count. For example, FMDv and FMDv serotype SAT2 cannot be in the same level as one is a subset of the other. At the time of writing, two levels of the classification of causes of disease have received particular interest in GBADs in terms of attribution (Levels 1 and 3).

³ Key terms used in this chapter are defined in Appendix A (section 0).

Figure 5.1. Hierarchical classification of causes of disease, with examples of interest for small ruminants. The arrow on the left-hand side indicates upper versus lower levels. FMDv = foot and mouth disease virus.

5.2.2 The challenges of comorbidity

In addition to the identification and classification of causes, disease causality presents a second important challenge. Comorbidity describes the co-occurrence of two or more causes in some pathological presentations, i.e. comorbidity occurs when an animal or group of animals experiences several diseases simultaneously. This might arise independently, such as when an animal or group of animals has both copper deficiency and PPR. Animals are routinely exposed to multiple causes that may or may not interact or accumulate towards adverse health outcomes. Accounting for comorbidity is an important process in the attribution of the burden of non-fatal diseases. Otherwise, there is a risk of double counting disease impacts, which would result in overestimating the overall burden of diseases in the system of interest.

5.2.3 Conceptual framework

The approach developed by GBADs for cause-specific attribution of disease burden considers both of these challenges: cause identification and comorbidity. Within the GBAD's analytical approach, attribution is preceded by the estimation of the all-cause AHLE. Then, the attribution process consists in quantifying the burden of disease specifically due to causes at the level of interest, using this all-cause AHLE as a boundary. With these different considerations in mind, GBADs' attribution framework can be conceived as a sequence of components and tasks, as described in Figure 5.2. Each step of this framework will be detailed in a dedicated paragraph in Section 0.

Figure 5.2. GBADs data and model flow chart to estimate the cause-specific burden of animal disease.

5.3 Methods

5.3.1 Step (1) – Causes of disease considered in the attribution process

Rather than developing the hierarchy of disease causes into an extensive list, GBADs currently proposes a pragmatic approach to attribution. Only levels and causes with available data are considered in the attribution process. The starting point for any burden of animal disease study is to decide on the causes of disease to include. The approach used to choose diseases will vary depending on available data, previous research, and the priorities of the study or project. For example, the GBADs' Ethiopian case study built on previous research regarding key diseases. Tsouloufi *et al.* (2020) developed a list of infectious diseases, which was then refined using expert opinion producing a systematic map of prevalence estimates for 29 diseases in Ethiopian small ruminants. This map was used as a starting point in the attribution process, further including non-infectious and external causes, as well as additional infectious causes of interest. An alternative approach is demonstrated in (RasmussenBarkema *et al.*, 2024), who chose 12 commonly studied and reported diseases and syndromes that are known to cause considerable production loss in dairy cattle systems.

5.3.2 Step (2) – Conceptual disease models

Fundamental to the estimation of the cause-specific burden of disease, are conceptual epidemiological models that describe the evolution of disease including onset, severity, duration, sequelae, recovery, and case fatality for different age and sex classes of animals within a production system. The GBADs approach models the impact of disease as changes in production. These conceptual models are schematically represented as an outcome tree for each aetiology of interest. Figure 5.3 provides an illustration of a conceptual model for PPR in sheep and goats, caused by infection with *Morbillivirus caprinae*. The first two levels of the tree describe the disease associated with this aetiology (e.g., PPR) as well as the significant outcomes (termed sequelae or syndromes, e.g., abortion). The third level describes the various health states that best represent each sequela (e.g., reduced parturition rate), as well as the time spent in each health state. The last level of the conceptual model describes the losses associated with each health state (e.g., reduced number of lambs weaned).

Using a similar approach to Devleesschauwer *et al.* (2015), disease models are then defined as computational models, which align the pathophysiology (the natural history of disease) with the input parameters needed to calculate morbidity and mortality of each health state.

Figure 5.3. Example of conceptual disease model for peste des petits ruminants (PPR).

5.3.3 Step (3) – Identification and collation of data sources

The cause-specific attribution requires a range of data types, including:

- Estimates of the frequency of occurrence (prevalence or incidence) for the different aetiologies
- Estimates of the frequency of occurrence, severity and duration of the different sequelae for each disease of interest
- Estimates of the frequency of comorbidity for the diseases of interest, which are needed to adjust the crude estimates of impact for each disease
- Demographic data on the population at risk, including current production parameters such as parturition rates, mortality rates, etc

The data should be relevant to the geography of interest, and ideally disaggregated by age and sex. In practice, such rich data rarely exist. Researchers may have the capacity and resources to collect additional data. In other cases, some assumptions and imputation are generally required. There is no single comprehensive and reliable source of data on the frequency and impacts of animal diseases. Instead, data may be drawn from a wide variety of existing sources such as notifiable disease registers, administrative data, surveys, and epidemiological studies. Potential data sources for this component are presented in more detail in Section 5.4.

5.3.4 Step (4) – Estimation of frequency by cause and sequelae

In step 4 of the attribution framework, the proportion of animals whose production is affected by the cause(s) of interest will be estimated. Peer-reviewed prevalence surveys are common and publicly available sources of cause frequency data. However, adjustments are usually needed to correct for several factors before obtaining an unbiased estimation of the proportion of animals which are affected, including:

- Test performance characteristics (sensitivity and specificity)
- Vaccination coverage in the population (for infectious diseases)

- Proportion of infected animals that are impacted by the cause
- Age of the animals tested
- Case fatality rate (for diseases causing significant mortality)

Examples of equations which can be used for these various adjustments are provided in Appendix B (section 5.9). These equations can be included in a Bayesian modelling framework that incorporates uncertainty and prior data. Such a framework allows the analyst to make use of the results from a range of field studies to produce a combined, corrected estimate of the proportion of animals that are affected.

Then, the corrected proportion should be converted to an incidence estimate to be used in attribution modelling. Additional adjustments are usually required for this conversion, especially for diseases of short duration or for chronic diseases that only impact production early or late in the natural history. A simple method applicable to diseases with extended seropositivity is presented in Appendix C (section 5.10). More advanced methods can be found in other references such as (Hens *et al.*, 2012).

5.3.5 Step (5) – Incorporation of disease-related changes in production parameters

Step 5 consists of incorporating disease-related changes in the production parameters, to reflect the different health states identified in the conceptual disease model. GBADs has explored different approaches to incorporating these changes in herd-level parameters, two of which are presented below. In both approaches, combined herd parameters are computed by combining the production of animals affected and unaffected by the cause of interest, based on the frequency of the cause estimated in Step (4) (Section 5.3.4). The herd parameters considered here depend on the species, cause of disease and sequelae associated with the disease cause. They may include parturition rate, milk yield, mortality rate, etc.

5.3.5.1 Approach 1

In this approach, we compute “average affected-herd parameters”, which reflect the presence of animals affected by the cause of interest for a certain duration (i.e., the average length of the sequelae). The remainder of animals are considered to be in an ideal health state.

The value of average affected-herd parameter H_i in the presence of specific cause i is obtained by combining the ideal value I of the parameter in unaffected animals, the value of the parameter D_i in animals affected by cause i , and the incidence b_i of animals affected by this cause, as per Equation (5.1). This equation assumes that the length of the sequela is similar to the time step of analysis, i.e., the animals affected during a given time step are associated with the affected parameter value for the entire time step.

$$H_i = I * (1 - b_i) + D_i * b_i \quad (5.1)$$

Depending on the type of herd parameter and available data on the impact of the cause of interest, the value of the parameter D_i in affected animals can be estimated either:

- **Directly:** for example, the mortality rate due to the specific cause in affected animals
- **Indirectly:** as the change from the current production level due to the specific cause, for example a decrease in milk yield. In this case, the change in current production e_i due to a cause i is applied to the current value of the parameter C as per Equation (5.2)

$$D_i = C * e_i \quad (5.2)$$

Given the relative lack of impact data for many causes of disease in livestock, a change in current production is anticipated to be the more common method as relative values can be used from countries with different production baselines. The two examples below provide more details on the calculation of average affected-herd parameters for a hypothetical disease A.

Estimating the average milk yield relative to the impact of disease A in sheep.

Setting the scene:

Ewes in perfect health in the ideal health scenario are believed to produce 32 litres of milk per month (I). Animals unaffected by disease A in the current scenario produce 24 litres of milk (C). The results of a literature review suggest that animals affected by disease A produce 50% less milk compared to current production (e_A). The estimated monthly incidence of disease A was 0.2 (b_A).

Calculation:

$$H_A = 32 * (1 - 0.2) + 24 * 0.50 * 0.2 = 28$$

The average monthly milk yield per animal in a herd where 20% are by disease A in a given month would be 28 litres in the absence of any other disease.

Estimating the average mortality rate relative to the impact of disease A in sheep.

Setting the scene:

Ewes in perfect health in the ideal health scenario have a mortality rate of zero by convention (I). Based on the results of a literature review, animals affected by disease A have a case fatality rate of 0.25 (D_i). The estimated monthly incidence of disease A for the period of interest was 0.2 (b_i).

Calculation:

$$H_A = 0 * (1 - 0.2) + 0.25 * 0.2 = 0.05$$

The average monthly mortality rate in a herd where 20% are affected by disease A would be 0.05 in the absence of any other disease.

5.3.5.2 Approach 2

In this approach, we compute “expected average herd parameters”, which reflect the expected value of a given herd parameter in the absence of a specific cause of disease. Individuals currently affected by the cause are considered to be unaffected, while the rest of the herd remain at its current (observed) production level.

In this approach, we will use the index “- i ” to indicate that we are considering parameters in the absence of cause i . The expected individual production parameter E_{-i} in the absence of specific cause i for individuals currently affected by cause i is obtained by combining the current average herd parameter C and the change in current production e_i due to a cause i , as per Equation (5.3).

$$E_{-i} = C * \frac{1}{1 - e_i} \quad (5.3)$$

From this, the expected average herd parameter H_{-i} in the absence of specific cause i is obtained by combining the production of currently healthy and currently affected individuals, using the incidence b_i of animals affected by cause i , as per Equation (5.4).

$$H_{-i} = C * (1 - b_i) + E_{-i} * b_i \quad (5.4)$$

A published example of this approach can be found in (Rasmussen, Shaw et al., 2024), modelling the losses caused by FMD in Ethiopian cattle. A simple worked example is set out below.

Estimating the average milk yield relative to the impact of disease A in cows.

Setting the scene:

Imagine a modern dairy herd in a high-income country, where the observed average production per cow (C) is 8,000 litres of milk per year. These cows suffer from various diseases which reduce milk production, including disease A. Disease A affects 40% of the herd annually (b_A), reducing the annual milk production in affected cows by 10% (e_A).

Calculation:

In the absence of disease A, the previously affected cows would each produce 8,889 litres, obtained as follows:

$$E_{-A} = 8000 * \frac{1}{1 - 0.1} = 8889$$

Thus, the expected average production per cow in the herd if disease A was absent would be 8,356 litres, obtained as follows:

$$H_{-A} = 8000 * (1 - 0.4) + 8889 * 0.4 = 8356$$

5.3.6 Step (6) – Comorbidity adjustment

5.3.6.1 Need for an adjustment

As highlighted in Section 5.2.2, groups of animals are often affected by more than one cause of disease. First, we will consider a simple situation, when these causes are independent and their effects additive. In this situation, the expected average herd parameters when both diseases are absent can be calculated additively, as per the example below.

Estimating the average milk yield relative to the impact of diseases A and B in cows, without comorbidity adjustment.

Setting the scene:

We are now considering a second condition, disease B, which results in a 5% reduction in milk production (e_B) and affects 50% of the herd (b_B). In this example, we consider that diseases A and B are independent and have additive effects.

Calculation:

In the absence of disease B, the previously affected cows would each produce 8,421 litres, obtained as follows:

$$E_{-B} = 8000 * \frac{1}{1 - 0.05} = 8421$$

However, there are also 50% of cows affected by disease A which also have disease B (or reciprocally, 40% of cows affected by disease B also have disease A). Therefore, 20% of cows have both diseases, 20% have disease A only, and 30% have disease B only.

Effects e_A and e_B being considered additive, cows previously affected by both diseases would produce 9,412 litres in the absence of those:

$$E_{-(A,B)} = 8000 * \frac{1}{1 - (0.1 + 0.05)} = 9412$$

Finally, the average production per cow in the herd if diseases A and B were both absent would be 8,586 litres. This is obtained as follows:

$$H_{-(A,B)} = 8000 * 0.3 + 8889 * 0.2 + 8421 * 0.3 + 9412 * 0.2 = 8586$$

However, comorbidity often leads to interactions between causes of disease, and it is often implausible to assume that disease incidences and production losses are additive. For example, cows with hypocalcaemia have twice the risk of developing ketosis than normo-calcaemic cows. Therefore, we need to consider whether comorbidity affects the incidence of diseases, their impact on production, or both at the same time. This is the purpose of Step (6), the comorbidity adjustment. The method used to incorporate disease changes into production parameters (Section 5.3.5) influences the way comorbidity can be adjusted for. Therefore, we will present two options for adjusting, corresponding to the two approaches described above.

5.3.6.2 Adjustment under Approach 1

Approach 1 was developed early on, in parallel with the development of the AHLE metric within GBADs. The current version presented in this chapter considers the reported frequency and production losses for a single cause of disease and does not account for comorbidities. At the time of writing, the GBADs team is working on an updated version of this approach. Briefly, this approach will adjust for comorbidity using population attributable fractions. The population attributable fraction for a given aetiology i and sequela of interest s ($PAF_{i,s}$) is defined as the proportion of all cases of this sequela (e.g., abortion) that can be attributed to cause i (e.g., abortive *Brucella* spp.) among the population. The population attributable fraction for cause i and sequela s can be calculated as per Equation (5.5) based

on the proportion p_i of animals affected by cause i and the relative risk $RR_{i,s}$ of sequela s for animals with cause i compared to those without cause i .

$$PAF_{i,s} = \frac{p_i * (RR_{i,s} - 1)}{p_i * (RR_{i,s} - 1) + 1} \quad (5.5)$$

Methods to adjust the population attributable fractions for comorbidities have been proposed previously, for example by the Global Burden of Diseases (GBD) programme (Hilderink *et al.*, 2016). Existing methods are currently reviewed to develop an approach most suited to the context of animal diseases. Updates on these methods will be outlined in future versions of the GBADs Technical Guide.

5.3.6.3 Adjustment under Approach 2

Rasmussen *et al.* (2022) described a modelling approach using Bayes' theorem, disease probability estimates, disease impact estimates, and inter-diseases odds ratios to estimate the probability of various disease combinations in a population and adjust impact estimates to reflect these comorbidities. In the present section, we will consider the simplest case of this approach, where we adjust for comorbidity in the case of two causes i_1 and i_2 , occurring with herd-level incidence values b_1 and b_2 . The adjustment can be split in two steps.

First, we need to adjust the incidence of disease. The relative risk of cause i_2 in animals with cause i_1 is represented by $RR_{2|1}$. We can calculate the incidence of each of the four categories of animals:

- Animals affected by both causes i_1 and i_2 , with incidence $b_1 * b_2 * RR_{2|1}$
- Animals affected by cause i_1 only, with incidence $b_1 * (1 - b_2 * RR_{2|1})$
- Animals affected by cause i_2 only, with incidence $b_2 * (1 - b_1 * RR_{2|1})$
- Unaffected animals, with incidence $1 - b_1 - b_2 + b_1 * b_2 * RR_{2|1}$

Second, we adjust the change in production losses. The non-additivity of losses can be represented by a change $e_{1,2}$ in current production when affected by both causes, which is different from $e_1 + e_2$. We now have the expected production parameter $E_{-(1,2)}$ in the absence of disease for individuals currently affected by both as per Equation (5.6).

$$E_{-(1,2)} = C * \frac{1}{1 - e_{1,2}} \quad (5.6)$$

Finally, the expected average herd parameter $H_{1,2}$ in the absence of both causes is now obtained by combining the incidence and expected individual production of each of the four groups, as per Equation (5.7).

$$H_{-(1,2)} = C * (1 - b_1 - b_2 + b_1 * b_2 * RR_{2|1}) + E_{-1} * b_1 * (1 - b_2 * RR_{2|1}) + E_{-2} * b_2 * (1 - b_1 * RR_{2|1}) + E_{-(1,2)} * b_1 * b_2 * RR_{2|1} \quad (5.7)$$

Estimating the average milk yield relative to the impact of diseases A and B in cows, with comorbidity adjustment.

Setting the scene:

We are considering that animals with disease A are 1.5 as likely to get disease B ($RR_{B/A}$), and that animals with both diseases lose 12% of milk production ($e_{A,B}$) rather than 15%.

Calculation:

The incidence of animals with both diseases is now 30%, obtained as follows:

$$0.4 * 0.5 * 1.5 = 0.3$$

The incidence of animals with disease A only is now 10%, obtained as follows:

$$0.4 * (1 - 0.5 * 1.5) = 0.1$$

The incidence of animals with disease B only is now 20%, obtained as follows:

$$0.5 * (1 - 0.4 * 1.5) = 0.2$$

Cows previously affected by both diseases would produce 9,090 litres in the absence of those:

$$E_{-(A,B)} = 8000 * \frac{1}{1 - 0.12} = 9090$$

Finally, the average production per cow in the herd if diseases A and B were both absent would be 8,500 litres. This gives an adjusted yield gap for disease A and B of 500 litres, instead of 586 litres prior to adjustment. This is obtained as follows:

$$H_{-(A,B)} = 8000 * 0.4 + 8889 * 0.1 + 8421 * 0.2 + 9090 * 0.3 = 8500$$

A global-level example of the use of this approach can be found in (RasmussenBarkema *et al.*, 2024), where 12 major conditions of dairy cattle were considered to compute global estimates. The authors intend to release future updates where other important diseases of cattle (e.g., fasciolosis, brucellosis and bovine viral diarrhoea) will be included. A national-level examples can be found in (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2022), modelling the burden of 13 diseases on the dairy sector in the UK.

5.3.7 Step (7) – Generating the cause-specific burden of disease

Steps (5) and (6) provide an estimation of average herd parameters considering the changes due to the cause of interest, for example in the form of affected-herd parameters (Approach 1) or expected herd parameters (Approach 2). These different parameters should cover the three areas of disease burden: production losses, mortality losses and animal health expenditure. These parameters should then be combined and compared to the relevant baseline situation to generate the cause-specific burden of disease. Ideally, this should be implemented using a population or herd model, to incorporate the interactions between the different production processes and population dynamics.

Here, we consider the affected-herd parameters developed under Approach 1. These parameters can be used to define a cause-specific scenario which models the occurrence and production effect of this cause in the animal population, in an otherwise ideal health situation. This scenario is then computed via the same DPM used to compute the all-cause AHLE (Chapter 4). Next, the changes in

population and annual production inputs and outputs estimated in the cause-specific scenario are compared with those in the ideal health scenario. The differences provide the parts of AHLE attributable to this cause, or cause-specific AHLE. The process can be repeated with the remaining AHLE for other causes of interest within the same level. Within a given level, causes not individually specified are captured in a residual category, making up the unattributed portion of the AHLE.

5.4 Data requirements

The approach described in this chapter for the cause-specific attribution of disease burden requires integrated data-driven models producing estimates that can be aggregated and disaggregated depending on the causes of disease considered. Such modelling requires an enormous amount of data for parameterisation, as described in Section 5.3.3, including both disease-related data (e.g., frequency, impact) and production-related data. These different types of data should be relevant to the species and production systems that is studied, as well as up to date.

The World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) curates the World Animal Health Information System (WAHIS), the most comprehensive and accessible dataset for the presence of infectious diseases in animals globally (WAHIS, 2023). However, this dataset has limitations, given that it only includes diseases listed by WOAH and is restricted to infectious diseases. In addition, the level and performance of disease surveillance varies heavily between countries. For example, countries where a given listed disease is endemic may only conduct minimal surveillance to meet their regulatory obligations. Therefore, disease frequency data from WAHIS must be corrected for reporting biases.

In addition, the GBADs approach to disease burden estimation requires generic data on animal production such as the prices of farm inputs and outputs as well as population size and structure (see Chapter 4 for more details). Sourcing rich data in the animal health domain can be extremely challenging, particularly if they are to be applied in a standardised way for internally and externally consistent modelling (VanderWaal *et al.*, 2017; Vial & Tedder, 2017). Given these challenges, estimating the cause-specific burden of disease is an ongoing and iterative process that will produce increasingly refined estimates with time. The data requirements and possible sources at different assessment scales are presented in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1. Data requirements for estimating the burden of disease by specific cause(s). Note that data required to estimate the all-cause burden of disease are covered in previous chapters and are not repeated here.

Data required	Details	Potential data sources		
		Global	National	Local
Frequency data	Data on prevalence or incidence of specific aetiologies and sequelae	Systematic reviews and meta-analysis, global databases (e.g., WAHIS, EMPRES-i)	Systematic reviews and meta-analysis, published surveillance data, notifiable disease data	Surveillance data, outbreak reports, livestock industry reports, veterinary reports, prospective and retrospective studies
Impact data ¹	Data on the changes in production parameters that can be attributed to specific causes of interest	Systematic reviews and meta-analysis	Livestock industry reports, veterinary reports, prospective and retrospective studies	Livestock industry reports, veterinary reports, prospective and retrospective studies
Comorbidity data	Data on the effect of comorbid conditions in terms of changes in	Systematic reviews and meta-analysis		

incidence and production losses				
Health expenditure data	Data on expenditure associated with animal health, including veterinary inputs, other products, and labour costs	Systematic reviews and meta-analysis	National registers and surveillance systems, drug production and trade databases	Surveillance data, livestock industry reports, veterinary reports

¹ Impact data specific to national and local populations may not be readily available, thus it may often need to be extrapolated from similar production systems within the global data.

5.5 Interpretation of results

Chapter 5 has introduced a framework for attributing the disease burden to specific causes, or groups of causes, of interest. In this section, we will discuss some elements to consider when interpreting and utilising the results obtained from these analyses.

5.5.1 Examples of attribution results

Applied examples of the attribution process are available via GBADs' [Knowledge Engine](#). Several of these examples relate to a case study conducted in Ethiopia, covering different species and production systems. The all-cause AHLE was estimated at national level using GBADs' [DPM](#). Attribution to level 3 causes, such as PPR in small ruminants, was then performed based on cause-specific scenarios computed via the DPM. The affected-herd parameters were estimated based on a review of the available literature, including both published and unpublished sources. The production losses considered for PPR in sheep and goats were a decreased parturition rate, an increased mortality rate, and increased animal health expenditure. Data sources specific to small ruminants in Ethiopia were used whenever available and completed by data from other countries when required. Preliminary results from the analysis suggests that the losses due to PPR reach 4.4 billion ETB (\approx 100 million USD) for 2021, for small ruminants in the mixed crop-livestock system. This is equivalent to 46 ETB (1.1 USD) per head per year, given a small ruminant population of 94 million head. The cost of PPR was equivalent to 5% of the all-cause AHLE, estimated at 80 billion ETB (\approx 1.8 billion USD) for the same year. These figures are provided for illustration only and will be re-evaluated when the analytical approach is finalised.

Burden attribution may also be conducted for Level 1 causes, as described in Larkins *et al.* (2023). The authors used structured expert elicitation, rather than population modelling, to quantify the burden attributable to high-level causes in Ethiopian ruminants. It is beyond the scope of the current Guide to describe this approach in detail, but the results provide a simple visual example of the attribution of the AHLE by cause. Figure 5.4 shows the outputs of this process as applied to small ruminants in the mixed crop-livestock system in Ethiopia. The AHLE was divided by type of loss (production- and mortality-related, respectively) before attribution to Level 1 causes. Infectious causes formed the majority of the AHLE, with a total of 48% of all health-related losses. Non-infectious causes ranked second (30% of losses), and external causes ranked third (22%).

Figure 5.4. Example of attribution of the burden of disease in Ethiopian small ruminants in the mixed crop-livestock production system. The all-cause AHLE (outer grey box) is divided between production and mortality losses, and then further attributed to infectious (red), non-infectious (blue) and external causes (green). Health expenditure makes up a very small proportion of the AHLE and is not visible in this view.

5.5.2 Choice of methodological approach

Attribution may be performed using various analytical approaches. The framework presented here accommodates different approaches, two of which are currently being explored by GBADs. The selection of a particular approach needs to reflect:

- **The study objectives**
- **The availability of data for the geography, production system, species and disease cause(s) of interest:** For some production systems or geographical areas, data may not be available in any form. Therefore, assumptions are usually necessary, and data may require statistical imputation.
- **The availability of data on the effects of comorbidity for the causes of interest:** Including comorbidity effects in the attribution process is very data intensive. It requires data that documents the combination of (comorbid) diseases experienced by a group of animals, as well as the associated production losses observed under each combination of comorbid conditions. Such data may not exist for the species and causes of interest.
- **The availability of human and material resources:** Comorbidity modelling requires significant resources to gather the extensive range of data required, as well as skills to design and implement complex disease models.

5.5.3 Limitations of the approach

It is important that GBADs' estimations of burden of disease by specific causes are interpreted alongside the data and model limitations associated with them. Attributing the burden of disease requires many simplifying assumptions, including hypotheses on disease causality, on the individual

impact of disease on production, as well as on comorbidity effects. Besides, estimates only reflect the current availability and accessibility of knowledge and should be updated as new data become available. Last, the attribution framework presented here also inherits the challenges and limitations related with the concept of AHLE. The AHLE relies on the notion of an upper biological limit of animal production. However, it should be interpreted as a boundary rather than an aim (see further considerations in Chapter 4).

The cause-specific attribution of the AHLE can be applied iteratively for all causes of interest within a given classification level. There will remain a residual, unallocated part of the AHLE, due to the limitations of available knowledge on a given system. This unattributed portion of the AHLE captures all the remaining causes of health losses which were not individually specified. The extent of this portion reflects the research gap for this particular production system. Indeed, epidemiological and economic research is influenced by many factors, such as the availability of funding sources. While funding may be particularly important for areas such as transboundary diseases, it remains less accessible for causes of poor health which are only locally relevant.

Finally, given the large number of parameters and hypotheses which are needed for attribution, sensitivity analysis is a useful additional step in the analysis. It can help determine how the choice of parameters affects the results and assist in uncovering sources of uncertainty. Such analysis can also guide additional work on parameter estimations by parameters which are particularly influential.

For these reasons, the approaches presented in this chapter are not intended to provide definitive guidance. Rather, they are presented here for readers to better understand these challenges and be able to interpret published results with those in mind. The methods described in this chapter have not been widely adopted and are still being refined before broader application. Future developments and applications within the GBADs programme will be presented in updated versions of this Technical Guide.

5.5.4 Utilisation of the results

The approaches described here can be adapted to obtain estimates at a sub-national, national or global scale, depending on the scale of interest for a particular production system. Attribution to specific causes can be used to describe the absolute and relative impacts of different causes in a given production system, as well as the evolution of these impacts over time. These results can be used in their own rights to prioritize health issues, inform animal health policy, identify needs for research investments, and support funding decisions.

In addition, attribution results can also be utilised in further steps of GBAD's analytical framework, to better understand the wider economic impact of specific causes of disease (see Chapter 6 for more details). Such analyses can help identify who across society is affected by particular causes of disease and compare the distribution of impact between diseases.

5.6 Summary

As indicated above, the current chapter offers guidance on how to attribute the all-cause burden of disease by specific causes within a given production system, at a sub-national, national or global scale. This chapter should be utilized in parallel with Chapter 4, which described how to calculate the all-cause burden of disease (AHLE). The attribution framework is based on seven steps, which are presented and illustrated in the main text:

1. Choosing the causes to consider
2. Constructing a conceptual disease model for these causes
3. Identifying, extracting and collating relevant data
4. Estimating the frequency of disease by cause and sequela
5. Incorporating changes in production parameters due to each cause and sequela
6. Adjusting these parameters for comorbidity when needed
7. Generating the cause-specific burden of disease

Further applied examples are also provided in the appendices (sections 0 to 5.10).

Several challenges are associated with cause-specific attribution. The availability of relevant data is particularly limited in animal health and economics. Available data may be impacted by different biases and quality issues and may not be applicable to the production system of interest. Burden estimates can and should be updated as new data become available.

The complexity of disease causation constitutes an important challenge as well. This chapter provides suggestion on how comorbidity may be accounted for in attribution modelling. However, comorbidity adjustment options are still under development within GBADs and will be described in detail in future versions of this Guide.

The guidance presented here aims to inform stakeholders about the GBADs approach to disease burden attribution and help them understand the process, its limitations and the interpretation of the results. The GBADs' team remain available to provide specific technical support for in-country implementation.

5.7 References

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5.8 Attribution: Appendix A – definition of key terms

To enhance interoperability across health domains and with the human burden of disease studies, wherever possible the key terms in this chapter are mapped to concepts with the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) available [here](#).

Table 5.2 Definitions of key terms used in attribution of losses to specific causes, including synonyms and Unified Medical Language System (UMLS) concepts.

Term	Definition	Synonyms	Mapping to UMLS concept
aetiology	The relationship between causes and the effects they produce.	etiology	C1314792
Animal Health Ontology	An ontology developed as a standardised ontology for animal health with the purpose of providing consistent, reusable and sustainable description of animal disease terms. It includes terms to describe the populations and demographics of animals together with the impacts of the disease on production. The AHO can be found on BioPortal: https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/AHO		
benign	A process that is not dangerous to health.		
burden of animal disease	The impact of disease in a farmed animal population, including morbidity, mortality, and health expenditure. For GBADs this incorporates the impact on the wider economy and human health. This impact refers to various metrics to measure death, loss of health due to, and expenditure on diseases and risk factors.		C4277729
comorbidity	The coexistence of two or more disease processes in the same animal or groups of animals.	multimorbidity	C0009488
conceptual disease model	Computational models, schematically represented as an outcome tree, that describe the significant outcomes (termed sequelae or syndromes) of each aetiological cause, the various health states that best represent the health loss from each sequela, as well as the time spent in each health state.	outcome tree	No similar UMLS concept
disease	An abnormal condition that adversely affects the structure or function leading to an inability to perform physiologic functions at normal levels; the outcome of which is a decreased efficiency of converting inputs such as feed and water, into outputs such as milk and meat.		C0012634
health state	Reflects a combination of sequelae that result in production loss which is not necessarily unique to a particular disease. Each health state is associated with a change in the value of a production parameter that reflects the severity and conceptually similar to a disability weight.		

litter size	The number of animals born per litter. It is measured as a distribution, for example proportion of single, twins and multiple lambs in a litter per adult ewe.	birth type, type C2239272 of birth, prolificacy rate	
morbidity	A measure of disease incorporating disease frequency, the clinical manifestation of the disease, resulting health states and changes in the value of production parameters.		
mortality rate	The proportion of the population that die during the study period. Mortality is a complex and multi-faceted parameter and may be defined differently depending on circumstances. In GBADs 1.0 the parameter "mortality rate" is used to refer to deaths directly due to animal health-related causes including: disease, injury, predation, acute nutritional deficits (e.g. starvation), and environmental catastrophe (e.g. droughts, flooding, wildfire). It does not include emergency slaughter or salvage slaughter as these are included in offtake if they have financial value.	death rate	C0205848
ontology	A terminology that includes explicit formal specification of how to represent the objects, concepts, relationships, and other entities that are in the terminology.		C1518584
parturition interval	The time interval between successive parturitions in the same female animal.	birth interval	C0005605
parturition rate	The inverse of the parturition interval. The value is the median or mean number of litters per adult female per time interval.		
Production parameter	Quantity representing the average value associated with a certain biological process (e.g., mortality, milk production, births) at the herd level. May be associated with a measure of uncertainty around said average value.		
sensitivity, diagnostic	The probability that a diagnostic test will produce a positive result given the animal is infected or affected by the disease of interest. The sensitivity of a test can be determined by calculating the number of true positive results divided by the sum of true positive results plus number of false negative results.	diagnostic sensitivity	C1511883
sequela	The pathological condition resulting from a disease or injury, such as abortion. Each sequela may be a consequence of multiple aetiologies and can be mapped to one or more health states resulting in a change in the value of a production parameter.	syndrome	C0543419
specificity, diagnostic	The probability that a diagnostic test will produce a negative result given the animal is not infected or affected by the disease of interest. The specificity of a test can be determined by calculating the number of	diagnostic specificity	C1511884

	true negative results divided by the sum of true negative results plus number of false positive results.		
statistical imputation	The substitution of some value for a missing data point or missing component of a data point	imputation	C2699638

5.9 Attribution: Appendix B – prevalence adjustments

In this appendix, we provide various equations to adjust prevalence estimates sourced from field studies in order to obtain an unbiased estimation of the proportion of animals affected. These equations are by no means exhaustive, and do not apply to all causes of disease or situations. The reader is advised to research the most suitable methods for their specific context.

5.9.1 Correcting apparent prevalence for test performance

The apparent prevalence AP (i.e., the proportion of all animals tested who tested positive) is adjusted for the sensitivity Se and specificity Sp of the test to provide the true prevalence TP in the study population as per Equation (5.8).

$$TP = \frac{AP + Sp - 1}{Se + Sp - 1} \quad (5.8)$$

5.9.2 Correcting seroprevalence for vaccination coverage

For infectious diseases where serological tests are used in areas of vaccination, the study's prevalence unadjusted for vaccination (TP) is corrected using the proportion of animals vaccinated and seroconverted (V) to estimate the seroprevalence due to infection IP as per Equation (5.9).

$$IP = 1 - \frac{1 - TP}{1 - V} \quad (5.9)$$

5.9.3 Accounting for the proportion of infected animals with production loss

Some infected animals will be asymptomatic, with no production affects due to infection. As such, the prevalence P of animals that are affected ("diseased") in a study is estimated from the prevalence of infected animals IP and P_{aff} , which is the proportion of infected animals that suffer from a specific production loss (Equation (5.10)).

$$P = IP * P_{aff} \quad (5.10)$$

5.9.4 Stratifying by age and sex

The previous steps produce a combined estimate P of the prevalence of affected animals, for each cause and sequela of interest. Ideally, this prevalence estimate should be stratified by the age and classes considered in the dynamic population model. In the remaining calculations set out below, we will use P_i for the prevalence of affected animals estimated for age-sex class i . However, it should be noted that this is not always possible due to lack of consistent age- and sex-stratified prevalence study data.

5.9.5 Correcting for case fatality rate

Prevalence studies may provide a biased estimate of the proportion of the cohort which has been affected when the case fatality rate of the disease of interest is high. Indeed, only animals which have survived the disease will be serologically positive. When the disease causes significant mortality in affected animals, the estimate (P_i) of the prevalence of affected animals in age-sex class i should be corrected to obtain the proportion of cohort affected ($P_{i,corr}$) using the case fatality rate f_i as per Equation (5.11).

$$P_{i,corr} = \frac{\frac{P_i}{1 - f_i}}{1 - P_i + \frac{P_i}{1 - f_i}} \quad (5.11)$$

The numerator of Equation (5.11) provides the number of affected animals, accounting for animals which died before seroconverting. The denominator provides a corrected population estimate after accounting for these deaths. A worked example is provided below.

Estimating the proportion of cohort affected by disease A in four age-sex classes in a sheep population.

Setting the scene:

The age-sex classes of interest are juvenile (< 6 months of age), sub-adult (6 to 12 months), adult females (1-10 years) and adult males (1-5 years). Serological studies of disease A were adjusted for test performance, vaccination coverage and the proportion of infected animals suffering production loss. This provided estimates of the prevalence of animals affected of 5% in juveniles and sub-adults, and 20% in adults. Case fatality rates were estimated at 30%, 20% and 5% in juveniles, sub-adults, and adults, respectively.

Calculation:

Age-sex class	Prevalence of animals affected	Case fatality rate	Proportion of cohort affected
Juvenile	0.05	0.3	0.070
Sub-adult	0.05	0.2	0.062
Adult male	0.2	0.05	0.208
Adult female	0.2	0.05	0.208

5.10 Attribution: Appendix C – estimating incidence

An estimation of the incidence of the cause of disease can be obtained from the prevalence of affected animals and the length of seropositivity for this cause. In the case of diseases with extended seropositivity, the average age in each age-sex class may be used instead of the length of seropositivity. Here, we provide a simple way to convert the proportion of cohort affected to incidence values assuming constant exposure over time with a given age-sex class and life-long seropositivity providing resistance to reinfection following exposure. More advanced methods can be found in other references. First, we estimate the average force of infection λ_i in age-sex class i , based on the proportion of cohort affected $P_{i,corr}$ and average age a (Equation (5.12)).

$$P_{i,corr} = 1 - e^{-\lambda_i * a} \quad (5.12)$$

Equivalent to $\lambda_i = -\frac{\log(1 - P_{i,corr})}{a}$

Estimate $P_{i,corr}$ represents the adjusted proportion of cohort affected, with individuals of different ages. The force of infection also allows us to estimate the expected proportion of animals which have been affected by a given age t within this class, $P_i(t)$. From this, the average incidence $b_i(t)$ during month t is calculated as the difference between the proportion affected by month $t+1$ and the proportion affected by month t , as shown in Equation (5.13).

$$b_i(t) = P_i(t + 1) - P_i(t) = e^{-\lambda_i * t} - e^{-\lambda_i * (t+1)} \quad (5.13)$$

The following text box provides an example on how the average monthly incidence by age-sex class can be calculated.

Estimating the average monthly incidence of disease A in four age-sex classes in a sheep population.

Setting the scene:

We consider that disease A causes life-long seropositivity in sheep. The analysis described above estimated the proportion of cohort affected (corrected for deaths) at 7% in juveniles, 6% in sub-adults, and 21% in adults.

Calculation:

Age-sex class	Average age in class (months)	Proportion of cohort affected	Age-specific force of infection λ	Average incidence per month $b(t)$
Juvenile	3	0.07	0.0242	0.0222
Sub-adult	9	0.06	0.0069	0.0064
Adult male	30	0.21	0.0079	0.0062
Adult female	60	0.21	0.0039	0.0031

Note that the assumptions presented above do not hold for every pathogen. Indeed, long-term immunity is not always the case, with some pathogens inducing only short-lived antibodies. Also, exposure to the cause of disease may vary strongly between age-sex classes. Finally, the calculation

does not account for the maternally acquired immunity, which is likely to modify the incidence in juveniles for many livestock diseases. In cases where these assumptions are not met, more complex methods for calculating incidence will be required.

Muraah Bannet
Rp. 81.900
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Muraah Bannet
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PROMO

DIGUNAKAN UNTUK :

1. SOP
2. SOTO
3. RAWON
4. KARE

DAGING SOP :

1. KANDUNGAN LEMAK 5 %
2. BERAT PER PACK : 350 GR
3. UNTUK 4 PORSI

DAGING RENDANG :

1. KANDUNGAN LEMAK 0 %
2. BERAT PER PACK : 350 GR
3. UNTUK 4 PORSI

DAGING BRISKET/SANDUNG LAMUR :
KANDUNGAN LEMAK 5 %

**DAGING SOP
BAHAN BAKU :**

1. WHOLE BLADE

**DAGING RENDANG
BAHAN BAKU:**

1. WHOLE BLADE

Chapter 6 Assessing the wider economic impact of animal disease burdens

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Abstract

Understanding the economic impact of animal health burdens on both domestic and international markets can provide valuable insights and useful metrics for the individual household up to the policymaker. The purpose of this guide is to offer an introduction to the computable general equilibrium (CGE) and partial equilibrium (PE) models utilised by the GBADs programme and why they are used to simulate the direct and indirect effects of market disruptions due to changes in animal health burdens. CGE and PE models can be used together to simulate how changes in the economy might fiscally benefit or harm people involved in the production and trade of goods and services, considering how different sectors and regions are connected worldwide. This chapter of the GBADs technical guide is intended to inform livestock production system analysts, researchers, policy makers and other stakeholders who may be interested in this topic.

6.1 Introduction: Purpose and scope of the present guide

The current guide is intended to introduce the use of general and partial equilibrium models for the evaluation of the wider economic impacts of animal disease burdens, as estimated using data input from the animal health loss envelope (AHLE) framework detailed in Chapter 4.

Given the computationally intense nature of the analyses presented below, these guides, unlike those in chapters 2-5 are not intended as a step-by-step guide for how the analysis can be undertaken. Instead, it is hoped that the explanations outlined below will provide users of GBADS methods and outputs with an overview of these techniques, methods, and data requirements, and how the results may be interpreted. However, a minimum level of economic literacy and technical knowledge is required to understand the concepts and methods described in this chapter.

This chapter is divided into two sections, section 6.2 covers general equilibrium models and section 6.3 covers partial equilibrium models. Guidance on interpretation of both types of models can be found in section 6.4.

6.2 General Equilibrium Models

6.2.1 Overview of the approach

6.2.1.1 General Equilibrium Model

Computable general equilibrium (CGE) models consist of a comprehensive and versatile framework for assessing the exogenous economic impacts or shocks of different types of adverse events, including animal disease burdens in livestock and meat sectors. The advantages of using a CGE model are that it accounts for intersectoral linkages among agents and sectors across regions throughout the global economy, allows for explicit treatment of bilateral trade flows between countries, and enables detailed national level economic welfare analysis for all regions in the model. Additionally, CGE models facilitate the assessment of policy interventions and the identification of potential spillover effects across different industries.

6.2.1.2 CGE model within the GBADs analytical structure

The analysis described in this guide is used within the GBADs analytical framework to assess impacts of animal disease burdens across the wider economy. The Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP) model is employed for this work⁴. GTAP is a CGE model that is commonly used to assess the effects of economic shocks, or unpredictable change in exogenous factors, on the international trading system, including international trade flows and transport margins, global savings and investment, and a comprehensive consumer demand system that accounts for price and income responsiveness across countries. An important advantage of the GTAP model is that it covers 141 countries across the world and allows the assessment of bilateral trade between trade partners in global livestock and meat markets. Results from modeling of the animal health loss envelope (AHLE) (see Chapter 4), calibrated for specific species and countries, can be used to create the scenarios to simulate the economic effects of disease mitigation within the GTAP framework. Changes in output, prices, GDP, international trade, economic efficiency, and welfare measures across regions are used to evaluate the economic impacts from changes in animal health.

6.2.1.3 Why the CGE model?

The GTAP modeling framework (Corong *et al.*, 2017; Hertel, 1997) has been used widely to investigate economic questions that are economywide in nature, including the impacts of animal disease and sanitary trade barriers on the global economy (Beckman & Arita, 2017; Beckman & Countryman, 2021; Countryman & Hagerman, 2017; De Menezes *et al.*, 2022; Miller *et al.*, 2019);). Using a CGE model brings several benefits, such as capturing complex interactions between different industries and economic players across various regions worldwide. It also allows for a clear analysis of trade between countries and provides a comprehensive evaluation of how changes can affect the economic welfare of nations involved. This approach ensures a detailed understanding of economic dynamics on a global scale, considering the intricacies of international trade and regional impacts.

6.2.2 Data requirements

The standard GTAP database version 10⁵ represents economic activity for 141 countries/regions and 65 sectors of economic activity, that can be described more generally by three broad categories: agriculture and food processing, manufacturing, and services (Aguiar *et al.*, 2019; Corong *et al.*, 2017). Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO) data, and country level profiles are also collected to identify the most important sectors for the country under study to determine

⁴ <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/>

⁵ <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/v10/index.aspx> Recent work by GBADs (Countryman 2023) has used this version, but future work will use the next version. Future editions of the guide will be updated accordingly.

how to aggregate the GTAP database for the analysis. Cattle, sheep, and goats are included in one GTAP sector and the corresponding meat products in another, while the other animals and other animal product sectors primarily include pork and poultry. The regional aggregation for the model represents different geographic regions, allowing us to represent trade patterns across the world. Version 10 of the GTAP database, which is originally calibrated for 2014, is employed for this work. The database is updated to 2021 by simulating observed changes in gross domestic product (GDP) and population growth and applying publicly available data from the World Bank (Beckman *et al.*, 2021; Beckman & Countryman, 2021). In GBADs analytical framework, AHLE estimates (see Chapter 4 and Gilbert *et al.* (2024)) are used as the basis for the design of shocks applied to the aggregated GTAP model to simulate the burden of animal disease.

6.2.3 Methods

6.2.3.1 Database Update and Aggregation

The first steps of working with the GTAP model are to 1) update the database, and 2) aggregate the sectors and regions.

Firstly, data must be collected from the World Bank for world population (World Bank, 2024) and GDP (World Bank, 2024) for both 2014 and 2021. The percentage change for each of the two variables, in each of the 141 countries/regions of the GTAP database can then be calculated. A shock corresponding to the percentage changes in GDP and population can then be applied into the GTAP model.

Secondly, with an updated database, sectors and regions can be aggregated into representative groups. For the analysis of economic impacts of animal disease burden, primary agricultural sectors are kept disaggregated, in addition to the pharmaceuticals sector. The other food and beverages sector includes processed agricultural, and food and beverage products in one combined sector. Remaining non-agricultural sectors include combined sectors for energy and extraction, manufacturing, and services. The regional aggregation depends on the country under analysis. Countries are aggregated to allow for the representation of general trade patterns across regions of the world, without focusing specifically on trade patterns of an individual country. Additional details of the database and aggregation can be found in Countryman (2023).

6.2.3.2 Scenario Design

With an updated and aggregated database, we design scenarios of shocks related to the improvement of animal health. The shocks are calculated as percentage changes in production and/or international trade, and then applied to the GTAP model. Different scenarios consider different magnitudes of production changes, allowing for a comparative analysis between outcomes resulting from different animal health improvement scenarios.

6.2.3.3 Challenges

The implementation of shocks to the GTAP model can be challenging since some sectors contain more than one product. For example, shocks to production in the cattle, sheep, and goat sector must consider the share of each species in the aggregated sector, resulting in a share-weighted percentage change in production for each scenario. However, it is possible to disaggregate sectors in order to implement exogenous shocks to specific products. This disaggregation relies on the availability of production and international trade data for all regions represented in the GTAP model.

6.3 Partial Equilibrium Models

6.3.1 Overview of the approach

6.3.1.1 Partial Equilibrium Model

The economic partial equilibrium (PE) model is used to assess how decreases in animal disease and improvements in livestock health impact the livestock sector of a country's economy. The impact of improved animal health translates through the input and output markets of the sector, as well as import and export markets, affecting the well-being of a country's economic agents. The PE model delineates impacts on the economic well-being of firms along the supply chain, consumers, and total economic welfare.

6.3.1.2 PE model within the GBADs analytical structure

The PE analysis described in this guide is used within the GBADs analytical framework to assess impacts of animal disease burdens across the wider economy. GBADs uses a vertically integrated partial equilibrium livestock (VIPEL) model to identify the impacts of improvements in animal health inputs, (such as livestock feed, medicine and vaccinations for animal diseases, and agricultural labour markets) on the supply chain of livestock and livestock products. The model also assesses output markets, such as the live animal and downstream meat markets within a country's economy.

Estimates derived from the calculation of the animal health loss envelope (AHLE) (see Chapter 4 and Gilbert *et al.* (2024)) are used as an input in the VIPEL model to measure specific counterfactual, or hypothetical, scenarios. One counterfactual example scenario is the increase in production of live animals at the farm level due to zero animal health burdens in the ideal, disease-free state (see Chapter 4). We simulate this scenario by imposing a shock (or an increase in live animal production due to changes in livestock health or disease status) in the VIPEL model. This shock needs to be applied in such a way that the increase in production reflects the improvement estimated by the AHLE model. Metrics of economic welfare, or benefits to both firms and consumers such as consumer welfare and producer welfare, are used to compare the distribution or redistribution of wealth from changes in animal health.

6.3.2 Why the PE model?

Partial equilibrium models are developed focusing on particular market(s) of interest. The underlying assumption is that the outcome of the market(s) under consideration is not impacted by other markets and vice versa. One of the advantages of using a PE model is to focus in on a particular value chain and break down the consumer and producer gains or losses at various stages of that supply chain.

Partial equilibrium models have a long tradition of being used in economics and trade for providing estimates of economic efficiency and distributional effects of wealth from exogenous shocks, investments, and policy changes, within the same framework (Alston *et al.*, 1998; Wohlgenant, 1993), and partial equilibrium models have been applied to assess animal health or disease shocks status. Animal disease spread models are used to assist in determining production (or supply) shocks that are then used in a static PE model that allows for changes in trade and multi-market behaviour (Paarlberg *et al.*, 2008; Pendell *et al.*, 2016; Pendell *et al.*, 2015; Rich & Winter-Nelson, 2007). Livestock disease outcomes can then be incorporated into a dynamic model of species inventory that delineates imports and exports by major trading partners (Nogueira *et al.*, 2011; Tozer & Marsh, 2012; Tozer *et al.*, 2015; Zhao *et al.*, 2006).

6.3.3 Data requirements

Data for the PE model are mainly in two forms: model parameters and level variables. Model parameters are used to calibrate the model for a particular economy, while level variables set up the baseline economy. Model parameters are mostly collected from existing literature and the global trade project model (GTAP) database (described in more detail on page 127 above)⁶. They include parameters such as cost shares and elasticities. Level variables are predominantly collected and calculated from the Food and Agricultural Organization Corporate Statistical Database (FAOSTAT)⁷, and include variables such as prices and quantities of domestic production, consumption, trade, etc. To be consistent, level variables are presented in million USD throughout this guide.

National-level data are used whenever available; however, regional data can also be used as a proxy when the national-level data are not available. If particular data are available in several sources, data collected or calculated from updated AHLE outputs and FAOSTAT are preferred as these sources are likely to be more up to date than the existing literature and GTAP database.

6.3.4 Methods

6.3.4.1 Calculation of the size of the shock

Components of the AHLE (i.e., the value difference for the current and ideal production scenarios (see Chapter 4)) are used to calculate the production shock. Since the meat sector is linked to live animal production and both live animal and meat markets are cleared separately, offtake data from the AHLE estimates are applied to identify changes in production. For calculation of the input shock to the PE model, results from the epidemiological scenarios (e.g. AHLE ideal state and AHLE zero mortality state) in the dynamic population model are utilized (see Chapter 4). For example, a positive shift in live animal production when moving to the AHLE ideal state from the current situation is shown in equation (6.1).

$$\text{Production Shock} = \frac{\text{Ideal Production} - \text{Current Production}}{\text{Current Production}} \quad (6.1)$$

6.3.4.2 Behavioural Equations

A VIPEL model is structured as an equilibrium displacement model (EDM) where endogenously determined variables are in their percentage change form (e.g., change in price, change in quantity). Behavioural equations of agents, such as live animal producers, meat processors, consumers, imports, exports, etc., create a system of linear equations. Parameters of these equations are expressed in the form of elasticities (i.e., price and substitution), cost shares, and shocks (as previously discussed above). To simulate economic outcomes that result from changes in animal disease burden, shocks calculated (as described in section 6.3.4.1), are used as an input(s) in the behavioural equations of the model. Shakil *et al.* (2023) lists and describes the behavioural equations used in the GBADs Ethiopian case study. Examples of supply side behavioural equations would be how producers react to changes in output price, input price, and productivity, while the demand side behavioural equations describe how consumers react to changes in prices.

6.3.4.3 Challenges

There are several challenges in PE modelling. Firstly, the PE model must be correctly identified and specified, and then calibrated and validated to individual countries or regions. Sensitivity analysis is

⁶ <https://www.gtap.agecon.purdue.edu/databases/v11/>

⁷ <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data>

required to assess how changes in the model affect forecasts. Secondly, identifying counterfactual, or hypothetical, scenarios within the VIPEL framework can be challenging. It is important to identify scenarios as consistent as possible with AHLE counterfactual scenarios. Thirdly, counterfactual scenarios might result in an entire change in production technology. These changes then need to be addressed in the appropriate behavioural equations and parameters. For example, Shakil *et al.* (2023) identified the AHLE ideal state as a special case in the VIPEL model. To accommodate this special case, the dimension of the system of behavioural equations needs to be adjusted. The special case also reflects the need to update parameters, such as cost shares.

6.4 Interpretation of results

6.4.1 General equilibrium models

The main outcomes from the GTAP model that are usually highlighted when assessing the economic impacts of animal disease are output and domestic market prices for the country under analysis, changes in bilateral trade, changes in GDP, and changes in economic welfare in each region. The outcomes of the GTAP model, and CGE models in general, represent aggregated changes by region, allowing for an overview of economic impacts in multiple regions, such as the results from De Menezes *et al.* (2022) for foot-and-mouth disease in Brazil and the spillover effects on countries that highly depend on beef imports from Brazil. However, although the GTAP model makes it possible to evaluate results on economic welfare and bilateral trade for different countries and regions, this advantage comes at the cost of lost detail and sensitivity at the production level when compared to a country-level PE model.

The GTAP model provides policymakers with valuable insights into the long-term consequences of animal health burdens, providing information to help formulate informed strategies for mitigating economic losses and enhancing the resilience of livestock and meat sectors.

6.4.2 Partial equilibrium models

The VIPEL model (the PE model within the GBADs analytical structure) is used to simulate outcomes (changes in prices and quantities in markets along the supply chain) of the economic burden of livestock disease and animal health. These outcomes are translated into several welfare metrics, such as changes in consumer welfare and producer welfare, and changes in the assets of live animal producers, that aggregate into the welfare of the entire economic sector. These economic metrics can be useful for comparative analysis, e.g., economic benefit of moving from the current state to the AHLE ideal state or to the AHLE zero mortality state (see Chapter 4). The outcomes from the VIPEL model are sensitive to the choice of the parameter values. Proper sensitivity analysis needs to be carried out before making any generic interpretation based on these results. For more details on the VIPEL model used in the Ethiopian case study, see Shakil *et al.* (2023).

6.4.3 Wider interpretation

Both PE and CGE models offer different lenses through which to analyse economic scenarios, and each demonstrate unique strengths and limitations. PE models typically focus on a single market or sector, isolating it from the rest of the economy to understand the effects of changes within that specific area. This narrow focus allows PE models to provide more details on the market or sector (e.g., economic impacts to both the firms and consumers along the supply chain) but can overlook the broader impacts across the economy. On the other hand, CGE models take into account the interconnectedness of all markets in an economy, capturing the ripple effects of changes across different sectors and regions. They provide a comprehensive overview, showing how adjustments in one part of the economy can lead to changes in the other parts of the economy. The choice between a PE and a CGE model hinges on the scope of the analysis desired: focused and detailed (i.e., PE), or broad and interconnected (i.e., CGE). Both models bring valuable insights, but their outputs must be interpreted within the context of their respective analytical scopes to inform policy decisions effectively. Perhaps most importantly, when used together the models paint a broader and more complete picture of animal health improvements on the economic landscape from the rural live animal producer to the urban consumer. Table 6.1 summarizes the main outcomes from each model.

Table 6.1 Main Outputs from Computable General Equilibrium and Partial Equilibrium Models

Economic Output	CGE Model	PE Model
Production	Percentage change in production quantity per sector, per country/region	Percentage change in production quantity per vertically integrated sectors of a particular country/region
Producer prices	Percentage change in producer price per sector, per country/region	Percentage change in prices of outputs from vertically integrated sectors of a particular country/region
Demand for production inputs	Percentage change in demand for land, labor, capital, and natural resources per sector, per country/region	Percentage change in demand for labor, feed, and animal health inputs at the farm level
Household demand	Percentage change in household demand per sector, per country/region	Percentage change in household demand for the final output
Exports	Percentage change in export quantity per sector, per country/region	Percentage change in export quantity per vertically integrated sectors of a particular country/region of interest
Export prices	Percentage change in export price per sector, per country/region	Domestic and export prices are same in the current version of the PE model
Bilateral trade	Percentage change in bilateral trade per sector, per country/region	Percentage change in import quantity per vertically integrated sectors of a particular country/region of interest from the rest of the world
Welfare	Change in economic welfare (Equivalent variation) in millions of dollars per country/region	Change in economic welfare (Producer and consumer welfare) in millions of dollars of a particular country/region of interest and of the rest of the world
GDP	Change in GDP in millions of dollars per country/region	-
Value of Asset Change	-	Change in asset value in millions of dollars at the farm level of a particular country/region of interest

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